

Deliverable D5.3.

Overview of energy consumption of different quarrying processes, connections and suggestions for reduction measures

Deliverable report

Deliverable No.	D5.3	Work Package No.	WP5	Task/s No.	Task 5.3
Work Package Title	Overview of energy consumption of different quarrying processes, connections and suggestions for reduction measures				
Linked Task/s Title	T5.3 Energy efficiency and environmental effects				
Status	Draft	(Draft/Draft Final/Final)			
Dissemination level	PU	(PU-Public, RE-Restricted, CO-Confidential)			
Due date deliverable	2024-05-31	Submission date	2024-05-28		
Deliverable version	v3				

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Document History

Version	Date	Comment
v.1	2024-05-10	Draft submitted to external reviewers within DEQ
v.2	2024-05-24	Revised version submitted to ZABALA and ANEFA
v.3	2024-05-28	Final version

Disclaimer

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DigiEcoQuarry project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (**WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers**) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analyzing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analyzed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow **a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities**. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BN	Bayesian Network
CAN	Control Area Network
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
DEQ	DigiEcoQuarry
DTH	Down-The-Hole (drilling)
FFS	Full-Field Solution
GHG	Greenhouse Gas (emissions)
H&S	Health & Safety
HFE	Highly Flexible Energy
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
IPP	Independent Power Producer
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy
LCSI	Local Crushing/Screening Interface
LOM	Life of mine
MIC	Maximum Instantaneous Charge
MSU	Mobile Sensitising Unit
MUL	Montanuniversität Leoben
MWD	Measurement While Drilling
NIR	Near-Infrared
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OPEX	Operating Expenses
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
PPA	Power Purchasing Agreement
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
PPV	Peak Particle Velocity
PSD	Particle Size Distribution
PV	Photovoltaic

QA/QC	Quality Assurance and Quality Control
RE	Renewable Energy
REST	Representational State Transfer
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TBD	To Be Determined
UPM-M	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid – Minería

1 Executive summary

One of the goals of the DigiEcoQuarry (DEQ) project is to enhance the energy efficiency of quarries. To achieve this objective, a set of solutions has been developed and deployed at the pilot sites participating in the project. These include novel technologies and a digital platform to integrate the operational data generated by the new systems and smart sensors in each quarrying unit process.

In this context, this report aims to provide a complete overview of the DEQ approach towards energy-efficient quarries. Specifically, it covers the following elements:

- Characterisation of the energy consumption in quarries and, specifically, in the DEQ pilot sites
- Analysis of the consumption and generation of renewable energy in the aggregate sector
- Detailed description of the technologies developed within the DEQ project that aim to improve energy efficiency along the quarrying value chain
- Estimation of the potential impact on energy efficiency, in terms of energy savings and costs and emissions reduction, from the implementation of the DEQ project in a given quarrying operation

The main outcomes included in this document are:

- General guidelines to support the decision-making process of an aggregate producer evaluating investing in a renewable energy project
- Comprehensive description of the DEQ's set of energy efficiency-related solutions and their expected contribution
- Estimation of the energy consumed by the ICT component of the project
- Integral evaluation of the potential impact of the DEQ project regarding energy consumption

Finally, the results obtained suggest that a quarry implementing the DEQ technologies has the potential to achieve annual energy-related CO₂ emissions reductions of 5% up to 12%. However, the actual energy improvements will be evaluated during the remaining phase of the DEQ project. Likewise, energy efficiency gains to be achieved in future applications of the DEQ solutions may also vary, depending on the specific circumstances of the operations.

2 Introduction

2.1 Background

Being an energy-intensive industry, energy efficiency has historically been among the top concerns of companies and it is a key performance indicator (KPI) monitored and reported by every mining operation. Energy consumption not only represents a large part of the operating costs (between 30% and 43% in the case of the sites in the project) but is also directly related to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Therefore, implementing actions to reduce it is of great importance from both financial and environmental perspectives.

When studying the different sectors within the mining industry, aggregates are undoubtedly the main contributors to global mineral activity in terms of production. For example, in 2017, sand, gravel, and crushed rock accounted for 54% of the minerals used globally (OECD 2019). Furthermore, the global production in 2019, including recycled and manufactured aggregates, was approximately 45 billion tonnes. Specifically, in the case of Europe, this sector is the most relevant among the non-energy extractive industries, with a total production of 2.99 billion tonnes during the same year, over 15,000 companies, 26,000 production sites, and 187,000 employees (European Aggregates Association 2021).

Besides its economic importance, illustrated in Europe by an estimated annual turnover of 15-20 billion (European Aggregates Association 2021), quarrying also contributes significantly to the mining industry's environmental footprint. Specifically, and addressing the topic of this report, construction minerals account for approximately 40% of the total energy consumed by the mining industry, given the large amount of tonnage extracted yearly (Aramendia et al. 2023).

In this context, one of the goals of the DigiEcoQuarry (DEQ) project is to enhance the energy efficiency of quarries. To achieve this objective, the DEQ project focuses on introducing further digitalisation to these operations, including novel technologies and a digital platform, the IQS¹, integrating the operational data generated by the new systems and smart sensors in each quarrying unit process. Additionally, within the project, the generation and consumption of renewable energy in the aggregate sector are analysed as complementary methods to reduce the environmental impact associated with energy usage.

2.2 Objectives

The specific goals of this report are:

- To provide an overview of the energy consumption in quarries and, specifically, in the pilot sites participating in the DEQ project
- Analyse the consumption and self-generation of energy from renewable sources in the aggregate sector
- Describe the different technologies developed within the DEQ project that aim to improve energy efficiency along the quarrying value chain
- Estimate the potential impact on energy efficiency, in terms of energy savings and costs and emissions reduction, from the implementation of the DEQ project in a given quarry operation

2.3 Limitations

The DEQ project is currently finishing the deployment phase, meaning that most of the technologies described in this report have been recently installed at certain pilot sites and/or will be tested in the upcoming months. Likewise, the integration of the IQS with the different digital services and expert systems is also in its final stage. Thus, actual impacts on energy efficiency are yet to be evaluated. Correspondingly, the final results and KPIs analysis will be carried out during the remaining year of the project.

¹ *Intelligent Quarry System.*

2.4 Organisation of the document

This report is organised as follows. In section 3, an overview of the quarrying value chain, with emphasis on energy consumption, is provided, including the analysis of the pilot sites participating in the project. In section 4, the general panorama regarding renewable energy sources and their application in the quarrying sector is analysed. In section 5, the DEQ approach towards improving energy efficiency is described, and each one of the technological solutions with an impact on energy consumption implemented within the project is examined. Section 6 provides an integral evaluation of the impacts of the DEQ project deployment in economic and environmental terms. Finally, section 7 presents the conclusions of this report.

3 Energy consumption in DEQ’s pilot sites

As presented in Figure 1, the typical quarrying value chain includes the steps of extraction, material handling, and processing. Additionally, the external transport stage corresponds to the shipment of the salable product obtained after processing to the consumer or final user. Regardless, this final step is usually carried out by third parties out of the site management. For this reason, the DEQ project mainly focuses on the unit processes in the extraction, material handling, and processing phases.

Figure 1. Quarrying value chain.

Quarries, like any mining operation, are diverse in nature. They can be classified according to their geology and deposit type, e.g., hard rock (to produce crushed rock), sand, gravel, and marine. Sites can also produce recycled and manufactured aggregates (European Aggregates Association 2021). Quarries also vary in the scale or size of the operation and method of extraction (closely related to the geology and deposit type). Accordingly, the characteristics of the site significantly influence the type of machinery and equipment to be employed in each unit process and, in consequence, the amount and type of energy consumed by the operation.

Particularly, in the DEQ project, five companies from the aggregate sector provide the necessary pilot sites to validate the technologies and solutions. The companies and locations of their pilot sites are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Pilot sites in the DEQ project

Company	Site	Location
CEMEX	Valdilecha	Madrid, Spain
CIMPOR	Alenquer	Alenquer, Portugal
CSI	Mammendorf	Magdeburg, Germany
HOLCIM	Pioltello	Milano, Italy
VICAT	Fenouillet	Toulouse, France

These sites reflect the diversity of quarries; not only do the types of deposits vary, but different extraction methods are applied at various scales of production. Table 2 presents the main features of the DEQ pilot sites and the relevant energy-consuming equipment in each case (Sanchez and Hartlieb 2022).

Table 2. Characteristics, machinery, and equipment at the DEQ pilot sites

	Pilot site	CEMEX	CIMPOR	CSI	HOLCIM	VICAT
General	Extraction method	Drilling & blasting	Drilling & blasting	Drilling & blasting	Dredging	None
	Main product	Limestone	Limestone	Andesite	Sand & gravel	Recycled material
	Average extraction [kt/y]	1,160	1,840	1,530	251	-
	Average processing [kt/y]	580	1,470	1,030	390	57
Machinery consuming fuel	Drills	✓	✓	✓		
	Excavator	✓		✓		
	Mobile crusher			✓		
	Wheel loader	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Trucks	✓	✓	✓		
Machinery consuming electricity	Dredge				✓	
	Conv. belts	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Screeners	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Crushers	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

As can be observed, the Valdilecha-CEMEX, Alenquer-CIMPOR, and Mammendorf-CSI pilot sites employ drilling and blasting to extract the material. Under this scheme, fuel (diesel) is consumed mainly in the extraction process, i.e. drilling, loading, and hauling. In contrast, the Pioltello-HOLCIM site extracts the material by dredging, which operates by means of electricity. In this case, diesel is consumed in a lower amount, mostly by auxiliary machinery in the handling of the products after processing. It is important to mention that Fenouillet-VICAT pilot site does not conduct extraction works; it produces aggregates from recycled material provided by nearby construction sites.

Differences between extracted and processed material are due to several factors:

- Need to extract overburden
- Extraction of waste, e.g. clay
- Processing of material from third parties
- Inventories handling (stockpiles)

Sections 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, and 3.4 characterise the energy consumption of the DEQ pilot sites through a series of relevant indicators for the period 2021-2023. Finally, section 3.5 discusses challenges and opportunities for further improvement and how the DEQ project addresses these.

3.1 Production

The indicators presented in this and the following sections are individualised by site, but due to confidentiality reasons, the specific operations are not disclosed. Also, the information is provided according to the availability of data in each case.

Figure 2 and Figure 3 present the yearly and monthly amounts of extracted material, respectively. While site 2 exhibits a gradual decrease in extracted tonnes over the years, site 3 shows a slight increase. Monthly production can vary considerably within the same year.

Figure 2. Yearly extracted material, in tonnes

Figure 3. Monthly extracted material, in tonnes

Similarly, Figure 4 and Figure 5 present the yearly and monthly amounts of processed material. Accordingly, the trends are similar to the extracted volumes.

Figure 4. Yearly processed material, in tonnes

Figure 5. Monthly processed material, in tonnes

3.2 Fuel consumption

Diesel is the fuel consumed by heavy machinery at the pilot sites and is mainly used in the extraction process, i.e. drilling, loading, and hauling. Accordingly, fuel consumption in sites 2-4 is strictly linked to the volume of extracted material, yearly and monthly, as can be observed in Figure 6 and Figure 7, respectively.

Figure 6. Yearly fuel consumption, in litres

Figure 7. Monthly fuel consumption, in litres

Finally, Figure 8 shows the average fuel intensity, i.e. fuel usage per tonne extracted. This indicator is significantly influenced by the operation's layout, i.e. distances between the loading points and crusher, as well as waste/overburden piles. Haul trucks at sites 2 and 4 must drive longer distances than at site 3 to transport the extracted material, meaning longer cycle times and, therefore, greater fuel consumption per unit of material.

Figure 8. Average fuel intensity, in litres per extracted tonne of material

3.3 Electricity consumption

Typically, the comminution process represents the largest share of electricity consumption in a quarrying operation, though if the material is extracted by methods such as dredging, this is also an important element of electricity consumption, e.g. at the Pioltello-HOLCIM pilot site. Figure 9 and Figure 10 present the total electricity consumed at sites 1-4, per year and monthly, respectively. In line with the production trends, as well as the fuel consumption evolution, pilot site 2 exhibits a decline in electricity usage in the analysed period. In contrast, site 3 shows a moderate increase, especially in the second part of 2023.

Figure 9. Yearly electricity consumption, in kWh

Figure 10. Monthly electricity consumption, in kWh

Figure 11 illustrates the average electricity intensity, i.e. electricity consumed by a tonne of processed material². Electricity intensity at the pilot sites is affected by several factors, mainly the rock type and hardness, and the presence of fines, i.e. clay. These factors explain the difference observed between the sites, of which site 3 possesses the most favourable conditions in this regard.

Figure 11. Average electricity intensity, in kWh per processed tonne of material

3.4 Energy share in operating cost

Energy is one of the main components of the operating cost or operating expenses (OPEX) in a quarrying operation. The preponderance of fuel or electricity in the OPEX is given by the characteristics of the operation, particularly the extraction method, and the conditions affecting both fuel and electricity consumption, as discussed in the previous subsections.

For reference, the average share of fuel and electricity in the pilot sites' OPEX is displayed in Figure 12. The relevance of each energy-related cost in the operating total is consistent with the fuel and electricity intensities of each site. For the analysed period, the total share of energy in the OPEX of these pilot sites ranges from 30.0% to 42.9%.

² Except in the case of the Pioltello-HOLCIM pilot site, in which electricity intensity is calculated over the sum of extracted and processed material.

Figure 12. Average share of energy consumption in OPEX of pilot sites, for the year 2022

3.5 Challenges and opportunities regarding energy efficiency

Generally, material handling and comminution are the unit processes that represent the largest share of energy consumption in a mining operation and, at the same time, show the highest potential for improvement from the energy efficiency perspective (Auwah-Offei 2016; Holmberg et al. 2017). Specifically, and as illustrated throughout this section, fuel consumption is mainly affected by the performance of the mobile machinery. While the consumption in loading is primarily influenced by the quality of the blasting, hauling trucks' consumption relates to their cycle times, affected by the internal distances but also by how the fleet is managed. Accordingly, DEQ solutions address these issues, i.e. drilling and blasting (see sections 5.1.1 and 5.1.2) and mobile fleet performance (see sections 5.2.2 and 5.2.3).

Electricity consumption in the processing/comminution phase is significantly influenced by the rock characteristics and the quality of the blasting. Additionally, further digitalisation and automation of the plant processes can translate into greater electricity efficiency. In this regard, the DEQ project also develops solutions for plant optimisation (see section 5.3).

Finally, further improvements can be achieved by integrating the operational data from all unit processes and analysing it from a wider perspective. In this regard, the data integration provided by the implementation of the IQS and the development of cross-sectional analyses (see section 5.5) is expected to unlock further gains towards energy efficiency.

4 Renewable energy in the aggregate sector

This section presents an overview of the renewable energy (RE) sources used by mining companies. Based on relevant literature, reports from companies and competent agencies, and case studies from recent years, it analyses the main drivers and restrictions to their implementation.

Three quarries participating in DEQ, i.e. CIMPOR, CSI, and HOLCIM, are also currently implementing RE generation projects. Though these initiatives are not part of the developments in DEQ, the experience undertaken by these pilot sites has been valuable input for the analysis presented in this section, helping to better understand the motivations and concerns in the decision-making process behind RE projects.

A series of key factors influencing the suitability of RE technologies for the aggregate sector are studied. Based on the findings of this section, a guideline to assess the suitability of RE applications is proposed. Finally, as an example, this framework is applied to the Alenquer-CIMPOR pilot site, and the results are discussed.

4.1 Renewable energy in mining

Due to deposits' geographical restrictions, there is not one single or general solution for all mines. In this regard, solar PV and wind energy usually receive more attention due to their significant roles in achieving carbon neutrality by 2050. The International Renewable Energy Agency predicts a 70% share of these technologies in the energy mix (IRENA 2023b).

The levelized cost of energy (LCOE) is a commonly used metric for comparing the economic competitiveness of different power generation technologies. It represents the per-kilowatt-hour cost of building and operating a generation plant over an assumed financial life and duty cycle. Referential LCOEs are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Referential LCOE for selected RE sources (IRENA 2023a)

RE technology	LCOE [USD/kWh]
Solar PV	0.049
Wind energy	0.033
Hydropower	0.061
Geothermal	0.056
Concentrated Solar Power	0.118

The LCOE is calculated by taking the total lifetime costs of building and operating a power plant (including initial capital, return on investment, continuous operation and maintenance, and decommissioning costs) and dividing these by the total amount of electricity generated by the plant over its lifetime (IEA 2015). Nonetheless, the mentioned LCOEs are meant to give an indication for comparing different technologies on a global scale. The LCOE can significantly vary from one region to another and should not be used as an absolute number for decision-making.

4.1.1 Solar Photovoltaic (PV)

This technology has seen rapid adoption due to falling costs and scalability. It's particularly suited for small-scale mining operations. However, efficiency is influenced by factors like temperature, irradiation, and panel maintenance (Tyagi et al. 2013).

4.1.1.1 Applications in mining

Solar PV is one of the most commercialised and, therefore, one of the most applicable opportunities in terms of alternative energy sources for mining operations. It offers a variety of economic and environmental benefits (Paredes Sánchez 2018). Applications in the mining industry reach from kW-size to several hundreds of MW, powering operations or injecting energy into the grid and surrounding communities (Choi and Song 2017).

4.1.1.2 Restrictions and enabling approaches

Several location-bound factors, such as space availability and predominant wind direction, are crucial for optimising the efficiency of solar PV installations in mining areas. Mining concessions often provide ample space, mitigating concerns about the physical footprint of solar arrays (Maennling and Toledano 2018). However, efficiency losses due to dust accumulation necessitate regular cleaning and consideration of wind patterns (Hussain et al. 2017). A significant challenge arises from the mismatch between the typical 25 to 30-year lifespan of solar panels and the operational lifespan of mines, which may not align (Sodhi et al. 2022). Solutions include selling post-closure solar energy to the grid (Bakhtavar et al. 2019) or employing modular, mobile solar technologies to create more flexibility (Laing O'Rourke 2018).

4.1.2 Wind Energy

Wind turbines, offering a lifespan of 20-25 years, require biannual maintenance to achieve a 60-70% utilisation rate (Chan and Mo 2017). The technology is maturing, with larger and more efficient turbines being developed (U.S. Department of Energy 2023).

4.1.2.1 Applications in mining

The Ragalan Mine in Canada is an interesting case study. The instalment of the 3 MW wind turbine combined with a flywheel, H₂ electrolysis, and fuel cell, which is necessary to increase the penetration from 15-20% to 35-50%, took the company five years of planning. By 2014, Glencore's intentions were to start small with a 3 MW wind turbine in that year and to increase in a later stage to a 9 MW plant (Energy and mines 2014). Congruently, the company built a second wind turbine in 2018 (Glencore Canada 2023).

4.1.2.2 Restrictions and enabling approaches

If wind energy is considered as a suitable possibility of generating energy for a project several restrictions need to be addressed. The location must be taken into account, and wind measurement needs to be carried out to estimate the amount of energy that can be produced on the site (Cristian Paul Chioncel et al. 2011). The life of mine (LOM) and the lifespan of the wind power plant need to be balanced, similar to the case of solar PV energy. The unpredictability of the wind and the utilisation of wind energy are some of the biggest concerns when considering this alternative for mining purposes (Ackermann 2012).

4.1.3 Hydropower

Hydropower power plants are available in various sizes ranging from 5 kW, so-called "pico-hydro", to over 10 MW capacity facilities, called "large hydro" (Soni et al. 2022). Nonetheless, in the literature, mining is found mostly to invest in large capacities of hydropower facilities, where mining plays a crucial role as an anchor energy consumption facility, often electrifying communities in Africa (Banerjee et al. 2015). However, the utilisation of flowing water systems often faces complex legal and environmental challenges that must be considered when evaluating the implementation of this RE.

4.1.3.1 Applications in mining

The mining industry is found to invest either in hydropower extension of grid capacities or in pump storage (Maennling and Toledano 2018). Pump storage requires two water reservoirs at different heights, connected by a pipeline, allowing for energy generation similar to a hydropower dam when water is released from the higher to the lower reservoir. For example, the Kidston Pumped Storage Hydro project, from Kidston Clean Energy Hub, located in Kidston, Queensland,

Australia, combines solar and wind energy with hydro-pump storage incorporating a storage capacity of 250 MW (Mining weekly 2018).

4.1.3.2 Restrictions and enabling approaches

The main challenges in harnessing hydro energy by mining operations include legal restrictions and the variability of regulatory environments across different countries (Guo et al. 2016). In Africa, for example, large mining companies leverage their investment capabilities to fund hydropower plants, which not only meet their own energy needs but also allow for expansion to support local communities. Conversely, in regions with unstable energy supplies, mines prioritise security over cost, opting for more expensive self-supply solutions when reliable energy cannot be guaranteed by external providers (Banerjee et al. 2015).

4.1.4 Geothermal

Forecasts indicate that geothermal capacity would increase to around 170 GW to reach the carbon neutrality targets for 2050. Though not as relevant as other REs, it can still play a crucial role by providing flexibility for future energy systems (IRENA 2023b).

Regardless, geothermal projects generally require substantial upfront investment, making them less suitable for small or medium operations, such as quarries.

4.1.4.1 Applications in mining

The Lihir gold mine located in Papua New Guinea consumes an annual amount of almost 65,000 GJ of electricity generated by their geothermal plant, equivalent to approximately 18 GWh (Newcrest 2023).

4.1.4.2 Restrictions and enabling approaches

The financing and the availability of geothermal potential seem to be the most crucial bottlenecks. As one of the newest levers of financial support, the Carbon Trading Mechanism (CDM) needs to be addressed. In 2020, it led an infrastructure project from Pertamina Geothermal Energy in Indonesia to success by providing the project with a stable source of income by selling its carbon credits to the world market (Pertamina 2020).

Geothermal energies are attractive under several circumstances. These circumstances include off-grid mining in remote areas, the presence of extractable geothermal potential, and the need for direct heat (Eleni Patsa et al. 2015), which are not usually aligned with quarry conditions, e.g. sites generally have access to the grid and don't need direct heat for their processes.

4.1.5 Concentrated Solar Power (CSP)

While effective in high-irradiance areas, CSP systems face challenges like high water usage and land requirements. Due to their high initial costs, they might be less compatible with the aggregate sector's conditions.

4.1.5.1 Applications in mining

The adoption of CSP technologies allows mining companies to lower their carbon footprint, aligning with global sustainability goals and potentially benefiting from carbon credit schemes. For example, Minera El Tesoro's 10-MW solar thermal plant in Chile replaced over 55% of the diesel fuel used in the mining process, reducing CO₂ emissions by approximately 10,000 tons per year (Paredes Sánchez 2018). Another example, also in Chile, is the Cerro Dominador CSP plant, which is primarily aimed at supplying power to the mining sector. It has an installed capacity of 110 MW and started operating in 2021 (Gacitúa et al. 2022).

4.1.5.2 Restrictions and enabling approaches

The primary challenges in deploying CSP include the requirement for high levels of direct normal irradiation (1,900-2,100 kWh/m²) found mainly in arid and semi-arid regions (World Bank 2021). Water scarcity in these areas complicates the operation of CSP plants, especially those using wet-cooling systems, due to their substantial water needs. The need for large tracts of land can lead to conflicts over land use and environmental disruption. Additionally, the high upfront costs associated with building CSP facilities, along with operational expenses for maintenance and cleaning of equipment, hinder wider adoption (Pascual et al. 2022). However, efforts are being made to adapt CSP technology for use in Europe through the integration of solar PV and CSP systems to maximise electricity production in the summer and utilise thermal energy storage in the winter for cost-effective energy storage (Aprà et al. 2021).

4.1.6 Power Purchasing Agreement (PPA)

Whereas the systems described in the previous subsections focus on self-generation, contract systems aim to outsource the electricity generation to Independent Power Producers (IPPs) and buy the energy directly from them under previously agreed terms fixed in a Power Purchasing Agreement (PPA) (Maennling and Toledano 2018).

PPAs offer mining companies a way to secure RE without upfront investment, making them an attractive option for aggregate firms with limited capital.

4.1.6.1 Applications in mining

The adoption of PPAs within the mining industry underscores a significant shift towards RE, a trend vividly illustrated through various global initiatives. For instance, in Chile, the mining sector saw a dramatic cost reduction in energy procurement exceeding 70% through PPAs post-implementation of Law 20,018 (Reuters 2016). Similarly, BHP has explored the potential of PPAs across its US legacy sites, aiming to harness over 0.5 GW of RE (Maennling and Toledano 2018). In Australia, the DeGrussa Solar project and the Coober Pedy Renewable Hybrid Power Station, initiated in 2016 and 2017, respectively, are also examples of the industry's effort to integrate sustainable energy solutions, achieving significant reductions in diesel dependency and enhancements in energy self-sufficiency (ARENA 2017). Furthermore, Glencore's 2014 initiative at its Raglan Mine in Canada leveraged wind energy expecting to benefit from substantial cost savings over two decades (Glencore Canada 2023). These examples collectively portray an industry progressively gravitating towards cleaner, more sustainable energy practices through strategic utilisation of PPAs.

4.1.6.2 Restrictions and enabling approaches

PPAs allow the purchase of RE from IPPs. This approach might be necessary for companies lacking the possibility of self-generation. PPAs are not bound to one specific production technique of RE. Therefore, a company building RE capacity can be more flexible to the site-specific requirements.

If, for example, capital expenditure is beyond the capacity of a mining company, the PPAs transfer the capital expenditure requirements and the risk to the IPPs. In contrast, mines pay a higher price for green energy as if they would generate it themselves (Maennling and Toledano 2018). In 2017, for example, 35 countries saw corporate PPA deals, with many mining-rich jurisdictions among them. Maennling and Toledano (2018) also mention that there are various PPA adaptations and opportunities, indicating the flexibility and diversity in such arrangements used in the mining industry for RE projects.

4.1.7 Hybrid systems and energy storage

Combining various renewable sources or blending renewable with conventional power can offer more stable and efficient energy solutions, particularly for remote or off-grid operations.

4.1.7.1 Applications in mining

An impressive case study and example of hybrid solutions might be the Chilean copper mining company Antofagasta PLC, which has committed itself to a 100% RE supply for its copper mines. The first of its mines in this endeavour, Zladivar, began its 100% RE operation in 2020. In this mine, the energy supply comes from hydro, wind, and solar power supplied through a PPA (Antofagasta PLC 2020). Antofagasta PLC goes even a step further also aiming to reduce its scope 1 and 3

emissions. The company is working with the Hydra Consortium to test hydrogen fuel cells and battery powertrains under real mining conditions (Copper Alliance 2022).

4.1.7.2 Restrictions and enabling approaches

Hybrid energy solutions, which integrate multiple technologies, including renewable and non-renewable sources with energy storage, remain expensive due to the need for oversizing power capacities. These systems, though stable for off-grid use, are not economically viable for smaller, grid-connected mining operations, e.g. a typical quarry (Ceran and Szczerbowski 2019). Moreover, adopting energy storage faces technical, economic, and regulatory challenges, complicating its widespread implementation (Bene 2023).

4.2 Renewable energy generation in the aggregate sector

4.2.1 Main drivers

Zharan and Bongaerts (2017) explore the increasing adoption of RE technologies in the mining industry, driven by sustainability and cost reduction needs. It notes that declining costs of RE, in contrast to rising costs for traditional sources, are enhancing the economic viability of renewables for mining operations. A SWOT analysis reveals strengths such as lower GHG emissions and operational savings, although high initial costs pose a significant challenge. The paper proposes a decision-making rule based on the principle of indifference between renewable and fossil fuel technologies, aimed at facilitating long-term economic planning. Although the study compares implementing renewables with the usage of fossil fuels, it underlines the economic importance of an investment decision, no matter if it is renewable or not. Therefore, one can conclude that higher electricity prices of grid-consumed energy might support the shift towards renewable self-generation.

The European Green Deal emphasises sustainability across various industries, including mining. The shift towards stricter environmental regulations means that aggregate operations must adhere to lower emission targets and implement sustainable practices. This includes innovations in resource efficiency and waste management. The more detailed targets to reach in the near future, e.g. by 2030 are a minimum of 55% cuts in GHG emissions, above 32% share of REs, and a decent amount of 32.5% improvement in energy efficiency minimum (European Commission 2024). These ambitious goals will be supported by regulatory frameworks which will affect quarrying companies. This should lead to CO₂ reduction, sustainable practices, and implementation of circular economy practices, as well as funding for sustainable technologies and an increase in market demand for sustainably produced products (Nodoph 2023). The production of aggregates from recycled construction materials by VICAT is an example of such practices.

Summarising, it can be stated that the main drivers for the integration of RE into quarrying operations are:

- Regulatory frameworks, e.g. European Green Deal
- Economic benefits
- Environmental, i.e. reducing CO₂ emissions

4.2.2 Guidelines for assessing the suitability of RE applications for aggregates

Quarries, though diverse, as described in section 3, possess several key characteristics that impact the decision-making process when evaluating the development of an RE generation project. These characteristics and their impact are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Characteristics of quarrying operations that imply considerations for RE projects

Characteristics	Impact
Small to medium-scale operations	The scale of energy projects might be below the utility scale
No 24/7 operations	Taking into account load profiles
Limited capital availability	Restricted investment capability
Unused mining concessions	Availability of land
Restricted use of heat	No need for heat-utilising technologies
Grid-connected	Given energy security but vulnerability to spot market prices
Self-consumption	The aim would be to produce energy when it might be consumed

Considering these characteristics and their implications, and based on the literature findings together with the experience of some of the pilot sites in DEQ developing RE projects, a framework is proposed to support the decision-making process of quarrying operations. Specifically, these guidelines can help identify the most suitable RE technologies to be implemented in a given site producing aggregates.

The framework is based on a series of key factors that determine the suitability of each available RE technology. These factors are described below.

4.2.2.1 Key factors for evaluating the suitability of RE technologies

4.2.2.1.1 Available sources

REs are dependent on their sources. If the company's location lacks renewable sources, will not be possible to supply the operation with the respective RE. Therefore, the availability of the source can be seen as the most crucial and, therefore, mandatory factor. The enabling conditions that must be assessed for the different RE technologies are the following:

- **High normal irradiation (HR):** 1,900-2,100 kWh/m² near-infrared (NIR) with clear skies is necessary (World Bank 2021). NIR levels can be found in the Global Solar Atlas (Solargis 2024).
- **Medium irradiation (MR):** It is considered to be always present. The viability of a solar PV project is dependent on many factors (Vodapally and Ali 2023), and at this point, the focus is on the availability of a source, not on viability. Therefore, a clear minimum threshold cannot be easily defined.
- **Wind (W):** to determine whether suitable wind speeds are usable in quarrying operations, the location of the site on wind speed maps, such as the New European Wind Atlas (2022), must be examined first. To better understand the wind speeds, wind speed measurements and aligning the system choice according to them are necessary inside the operation. These measurements should be done over one year upfront (Cetinay et al. 2017).
- **Geothermal (G):** a geothermal resource assessment needs to be done to evaluate if geothermal potential is present. There is a variety of possible assessments. According to Ashat et al. (2019), the most widely accepted method is the numerical reservoir model which is one of six classes described in Clothworthy et al. (2006).
- **Flowing water (FW):** checking if access to a flowing water system is present and assessing all constraints, including environmental, operational, and regulatory ones (Stoll et al. 2017).
- **Independent power producers (IPP):** research if IPPs are available in the region where the company operates.

4.2.2.1.2 Investment capability

Assesses the capability of upfront investment with **high (H)**, **medium (M)**, or **low (L)**. The limits between these categories might be difficult to define. Although the LCOE gives an indication of the energy costs per kWh for each system, it can not be used solely as a decision-making tool on its own. Quarries are usually relatively small compared to operations discussed

in several case studies of REs implemented in mining, meaning below a utility-scale energy consumption (e.g. <2MW). Instead, the economic assessment must be done from a broader perspective. The suitability for low investment capability might only be given for solar and wind, and the lowest for signing a PPA, which is not in need of upfront investment. Economic factors influencing the investment decisions of a mining company into renewables consist of upfront capital costs, the cost of capital, operational costs, subsidies for REs, economic viability, risk mitigation, and insurance products (Maennling and Toledano 2018).

4.2.2.1.3 Load profile

A load profile is a graphical representation of the variation in energy consumption over a specific period, typically 24 hours (Issi and Kaplan 2018). The following classes were defined:

- **Continuous (C):** the energy is produced continuously throughout the day and night without the necessity of energy storage.
- **Discontinuous (DC):** the energy is produced discontinuously, with high variability during the day and night. No stable energy supply can be provided without further storage systems.
- **Daytime-focused (DTF):** the energy is delivered only during the daytime, specifically during sunny, cloudless weather periods.

It is assumed that the primary goal of the RE implementation is the self-consumption of the produced energy. Therefore, the quarrying company should assess its load profiles for optimal synchronisation of energy production and consumption.

4.2.2.1.4 Land availability

The availability of land is rated from **High (H) to Low (L)**. It can change significantly over a quarry's lifetime because the longer the site operates, the higher the share of the reclaimed and, therefore, unused land inside the mining concession.

4.2.2.1.5 Life of Mine (LOM)

For the proposed guideline, LOM is categorised into three levels: **less than 10 years, 10 to 25 years, and more than 25**.

When considering self-generation, investment requires time to return to the quarrying company. Meanwhile, in PPAs, prices are often coupled to the length of the contract. This means longer contracts supply cheaper energy even though they are already accessible starting from five years onwards (Alova 2018). For example, a 15-year-based contract not only offers price stability, but also the consumed energy prices are likely to be cheaper because of the price coupling to the life of the energy generating system. Therefore, the ranges proposed (<10, 10-25, and >25 years) have been defined according to the average lifetime of the different technologies. Whereas the implementation of solar energy can already pay off within its first 10 years, the operation can last up to 25 years. The same longevity applies to wind energy systems and CSPs (IRENA 2023a); under certain circumstances, geothermal power plants might last for 50 years (illumine 2023). Hydropower plants can even exceed this lifespan (Renewables First 2024). An important statement to mention is that renewables are more likely to be implemented in a newly constructed mine than in an already existing one. This is because of the better alignment of the lifespans of the RE systems with the needs of the mining operation (Strazzabosco et al. 2022).

4.2.2.1.6 Personnel capacities and level of knowledge

This factor is rated as **high (H), medium (M), and low (L)**. It aims to give an indication of the scope of the workload expected for the implementation and operation regarding each solution in comparison with the rest. The findings in the literature, supported by the experience of the DEQ's pilot sites, reveal that the personnel capacities and the level of knowledge inside the company regarding a specific RE solution are important bottlenecks which remain often underestimated (Maennling and Toledano 2018; Alova 2018). It is also related to the potential need for an additional workforce for the operation of the power plants to be implemented.

4.2.2.1.7 Energy storage

This factor determines if the company is willing to consider extra investment for storage capacities if the selected RE solution requires them, given the different load profiles of RE production.

4.2.2.2 Tool to rank the suitability of each RE

The objective is to evaluate the compatibility between the requirements of each RE technology and the needs and conditions of a company evaluating the implementation of a RE project. The key factors described in the previous subsection are the categories in which the evaluation is conducted.

The tool proposed consists of the table presented in Figure 13.

RE	Available sources						Investment capability			Load profile			Land availability			LOM			Personnel capacities & level of knowledge			Energy storage		Score
	HR	MR	W	G	FW	IPP	H	M	L	C	DC	DTF	H	M	L	<10	10-25	>25	H	M	L	Yes	No	
Solar	■	■					■	■	■		■	■	■			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	
Wind			■				■	■	■		■	■	■			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	
Hydro					■	■	■	■	■		■	■	■			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	
Geothermal					■	■	■	■	■		■	■	■			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	
CSP	■						■	■	■		■	■	■			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	
PPA						■	■	■	■		■	■	■			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	

Figure 13. Guideline tool for REs suitability assessment

The table sections are the following:

- The first column presents the name of each RE considered
- The following columns are grouped in sets, where each set corresponds to a key factor and the individual columns to their respective levels or categories
- The REs are specified in the rows
- The coloured levels in each row correspond to those compatible with the respective RE, in each case
- In the last column, the total score representing the suitability of each RE is indicated

Then, the evaluation is carried out according to these considerations:

- For the first key factor, i.e. “Available sources”, the company must mark all the columns representing a source that is available on the site
- For the following key factors, only one column must be selected
- The score for each RE is represented by the total of selections that fall within the coloured (compatible) area, respectively; however, compatibility in the first factor –“Available source”- is mandatory, i.e. if the source is not present at the site, such RE cannot be considered, naturally

4.2.2.3 Case study: Alenquer-CIMPOR site

To illustrate the application of the proposed guidelines, the evaluation has been conducted for the Alenquer-CIMPOR pilot sites.

1. **Available sources: High normal irradiation (HR), medium irradiation (MR), wind (W).** the area has high normal irradiation, also medium irradiation, and enough wind present (wind turbines from other companies operate near the location).

2. **Investment capability: Low (L).** As with many aggregate sites, the capital cost of this kind of project is one of the major restrictions.
3. **Load profile: Daytime-focused (DTF).** Given the working hours scheme at the site, the energy consumption is concentrated during the day-time.
4. **Land availability: High (H).**
5. **LOM: 10-25 years.**
6. **Personnel capacities and level of knowledge: Low (L).** Given their scale, the technical capacity and expertise needed for implementing and maintaining any RE project are challenges for operations with a limited workforce
7. **Energy storage: No**

The results of the evaluation can be observed in Figure 14.

RE	Available sources						Investment capability			Load profile			Land availability			LOM			Personnel capacities & level of knowledge			Energy storage		Score	
	HR	MR	W	G	FW	IPP	H	M	L	C	DC	DTF	H	M	L	<10	10-25	>25	H	M	L	Yes	No		
Solar	X	X	X						X			X	X			X				X			X		7
Wind	X	X	X						X			X	X			X				X			X		4
Hydro	X	X	X						X			X	X			X				X			X		
Geothermal	X	X	X						X			X	X			X				X			X		
CSP	X	X	X						X			X	X			X				X			X		4
PPA	X	X	X						X			X	X			X				X			X		

Figure 14. Application of the guideline tool for REs suitability at Alenquer-CIMPOR

According to the assessment, the most suitable RE, with a score of 7, would be Solar PV. This outcome is in line with the company's decision of the recently implemented Solar PV project at the site. CSP and wind are seen as less suitable because of their higher investment costs and the need for energy storage in case of implementation. PPAs could also be a viable alternative if IPPs are present in the region, but this would need to be verified.

5 DEQ solutions towards energy efficiency

The DEQ project follows a holistic approach, addressing each one of the value chain stages with novel technologies and smart sensors. Moreover, builds a digital environment in which the data generated is integrated, stored, and analysed to provide critical insights to operation management, the IQS.

In this section, the technologies that directly impact the energy efficiency of each unit process are described. These technologies are different in nature, e.g., production machinery or smart sensors and supporting software (expert systems). At the same time, their effect on reducing energy consumption is materialised through distinct mechanisms, e.g. the machine possesses a superior energy efficiency than reference equipment, or the system provides the tools for optimising the operation and, in consequence, reducing the energy consumption.

The following subsections address these technologies. In each case, a summary table with the key features is presented (see Tables 5-14). Additionally, a detailed description of the system is provided, together with the expected impact on energy and other important aspects, such as productivity, safety, environment, and social acceptance.

5.1 Extraction

5.1.1 Drilling – Sandvik

Table 5. Summary Sandvik

Key information	Description
DEQ partner	Sandvik
Name of the technology	Long-piston rock drill technology (XL-method)
Type	Machinery, drill rig
Technology Readiness Level	XL-drilling method: TRL 7 (aiming to reach TRL 9 by the end of the project) Automation: TRL 5-6
Installed power	210 kW
Energy efficiency improvement	16% fuel consumption reduction (compared to state-of-the-art top hammer drilling)

5.1.1.1 Description

Sandvik’s contribution to the DEQ project focuses on adapting its XL-method to quarrying hole size, developing equipment platforms, and verifying performance. In parallel, support system technology and drilling automation have been developed, with the underlying target of improving drilling productivity and the derivative process stages in quarrying applications.

The core of the development is the long piston rock drill in the 30 kW power range, matching drill tools, the feed system, and the drilling carrier to support the drill.

The low-frequency long-pulse impact provides a high instantaneous and nominal percussion energy in an optimised impact pulse shape and stroke dynamic behaviour. The two main advantages are the long duration of the impact pulse, providing consistent drive into the rock, and the efficiency gains by avoiding repeated losses in the rock contact forming stage in the early part of the impact pulse. The efficiency and frequency also support the increase in the life of drilling tools as they are less subject to cyclical strain-stress loading. These are also confirmed and monitored with Sandvik RockPulse technology, which is being modified from smaller hole sizes to quarrying diameters of rock drills and tools.

The drill tools being developed are based on a tubular concept, with a high thread rise compared to conventional solutions. In addition to fatigue endurance and increased lifetime, the structure offers easier handling of the threads, simplifying

automated processes and reducing the need for human intervention during the drilling process. Consequently, the feed system needs to be adapted to accept and be able to handle the tools, including modifications to the feeding mechanism and power generation itself.

Key platform changes include modifications to the rod handling mechanisms, rock drill oil filtering circuits, hydraulic power circuitry, dust management, and feed/boom structure mechanics.

One of the main developments focuses on the production and consumption of flushing air. Air generation is the primary energy consumer and, thus, a significant opportunity for savings. However, in down-the-hole (DTH) drilling, the hammer is -inefficiently- driven with pneumatic air, and consequently, there is an excessive amount of air available for flushing the holes and cleaning the cuttings out of the hole while drilling. This is simply the result of air having to be generated with a larger compressor capable of a high airflow to drive the hammer. This airflow is then expelled from the hammer once utilised in the work cycle. For this reason, DTH drilling is well suited for broken ground conditions and large hole diameters, whereas, with the new top hammer long-piston technology, enough air must be added in parallel with the hydraulic impact process. The amount of air will be a trade-off between sufficient flushing, compressor, and air circuit sizing (affecting cost and energy consumption), energy usage, system dimensions, and applicability to different rock conditions.

Figure 15. Long-piston rock drill rig performing test drilling

5.1.1.2 Connectivity

To increase drilling productivity through automation and data analysis, appropriate connectivity and data transfer means must be implemented, including access to the data. For drill rig connectivity, the following technologies have been studied and developed.

5.1.1.2.1 Onboard interface for machine control and automation

The onboard interface is a machine control, and the automation interface is a REST API service on the drill control system, providing standardised, safe, and secure open access to the control system and its data. A first version has been developed and trialed with several third parties. This interface allows third-party devices to be seamlessly and easily integrated with onboard systems, increasing the machine data's transparency and shareability for process optimisation beyond OEM systems. The interface has been demonstrated on two occasions, with three OEMs connecting their respective solutions to the available data.

5.1.1.2.2 System for data transfer to the cloud and data accessibility

Cloud data transfer development has included the definition of suitable data content and packaging for transfer into the cloud service, together with logging and storing of the data. As described above, a control system integrated data collection and reporting solution has several advantages. Still, a deeper analysis of how the data collection is implemented and how the data is drawn from different sources and databases in the drill control system is required. Also, routing this data for transmission needs to be planned, as well as the hardware and software solutions to be used. The hardware layer of data transfer is implemented via an external remote access unit, connected and controlled through the drill control system, offering versatile possibilities for communication. Current technological solutions include Bluetooth and cellular (4G/LTE) data transfer, Wi-Fi client, and WAN capability for connecting to external networks. In addition, the same physical unit has been integrated to support the open interface solution mentioned above, acting as a Wi-Fi client for external connections (such as displaying the drill screen remotely).

5.1.1.2.3 On-site local server solution and related technologies for real-time process control

The local server solution is a client-server architecture, where drills act as clients connecting to a central server located in the site's IT architecture. Connectivity is generated through an on-site network into which the drills can connect using the remote access unit or an external network radio. The local server provides near real-time visibility to the data as high reporting and update rates can be used, and the system is dedicated to a single site only. The core server is SQL-based, offering REST API and SQL access to query and transfer data to external systems. Transfer of drill plans and as-drilled information with drill & blast solutions in a single-click transfer pipeline is also supported.

As part of the development, it has been evaluated how a new connectivity concept could be made available to equipment already deployed to operational sites and what activities would be needed to successfully transition from legacy technologies to a new solution. These evaluations have been made from a user and manufacturer perspective.

5.1.1.3 Impact on energy efficiency

A vast amount of test drilling has confirmed significant improvements in drilling speed and energy consumption compared to state-of-the-art top hammer drilling. Figure 16 shows the improvements in productivity and energy efficiency. A fuel consumption reduction of 16% has been observed compared to state-of-the-art top hammer drilling.

Figure 16. Change in power distribution and variation in drilling and energy efficiency

Additionally, utilising the XL-method with the developed drill tools produces higher-quality blast holes than conventional drilling. As the deviation/bending of the holes is considerably lower, the blasting can achieve better results. Straight holes play a major role in the quest to achieve optimal fragmentation. Consequently, by optimising the blasting outcome, energy consumption per unit can be improved in downstream processes, i.e. loading, hauling, and comminution.

5.1.1.4 Other impacts

The impact of the method is not limited solely to the improvement of energy consumption but also encompasses other significant effects.

5.1.1.4.1 Productivity

Significant productivity improvements with the XL-method compared to conventional drilling have been demonstrated by test drilling. According to what has been observed during the trials, the penetration rate increased by 10% to 20%. This means that more drilling can be accomplished in a given timeframe with the same amount of fuel consumption. Increased productivity translates to higher output per unit of time, allowing for quicker completion of tasks and potentially increasing overall production capacity.

5.1.1.4.2 Safety

The increased penetration rate per minute may reduce the overall drilling time required, potentially minimising the exposure of workers to hazardous conditions associated with drilling operations. Reduced drilling time can also lower the fatigue levels of operators, which could contribute to improved alertness and safety awareness on the site.

5.1.1.4.3 Environment

Lower fuel consumption translates directly to reduced GHG emissions and environmental footprint associated with the quarrying operation.

5.1.1.4.4 Social acceptance

Adopting technologies that prioritise productivity, safety, and environmental sustainability can enhance the reputation of the quarrying operation within the community. Improved productivity and efficiency can lead to better job satisfaction among workers as they may experience less stress related to meeting production targets.

5.1.1.5 Limitations and future work

Given that the minimum hole diameter for this application stands at 140 mm, it is ideally suited for implementation within larger quarrying operations. However, its suitability for smaller quarries with lower production volumes may be limited by cost considerations. Additionally, it's worth noting that top-hammer percussive drilling may not be the most efficient choice for softer rock types.

Future endeavours in this field will focus on advancing automation technologies to further streamline and enhance drilling processes.

5.1.2 Blasting – MAXAM

Table 6. Summary MAXAM

Key information	Description
DEQ partner	MAXAM
Name of the technology	RIOBLAST MAXAM BLAST CENTER X-Truck X-Logger RIOFLEX QY – SMART System
Type	Innovative explosives, loading systems, and supporting digital tools
Technology Readiness Level	Digital tools: TRL 8-9 RIOFLEX explosive for quarrying operations: TRL 7-8 (the original product is on TRL 9 and being operated worldwide)
Installed power	N/A
Energy efficiency improvement	5-10% fuel consumption reduction (expected) in loading 2-5% electricity consumption reduction (expected) in crushing

5.1.2.1 Description

MAXAM’s efforts in the DEQ project are focused on adapting their technologies and services, which are already being applied in large-scale mines worldwide, for the quarrying environment. Specifically, the products tested at the Valdilecha-CEMEX pilot site are part of MAXAM’s X-Energy solution which comprises a set of digital tools, i.e. RIOBLAST, MAXAM Blast Center, X-Truck, and X-Logger, and an innovative explosive, i.e. the RIOFLEX QY – Smart System.

5.1.2.1.1 Digital tools and QA/QC methodology

Mining processes are composed of inter-connected operations, which raises the importance of controlling key information flow coming from different areas. MAXAM’s X-Energy solution combines a full range of digital tools and capabilities allowing a reliable integration between drilling and blasting with long-term mining optimisation programs. Each tool is described below.

5.1.2.1.1.1 MAXAM Blast Center

A cloud-based hub that enables the full digitalisation, management, traceability, and analysis of the blasting services. It integrates the digital tools RIOBLAST, X-Logger, and X-Truck.

The data collected on the field with the X-Logger is automatically synchronised with Blast Center, allowing the evaluation of the blast performance by comparing the designed blasting plan with the actual one.

5.1.2.1.1.2 RIOBLAST

RIOBLAST is a 3D blast design and simulation software specially developed to help blasters and engineers add value to their daily work. It offers a simplified and intuitive interface through which it is possible to design, analyse, and simulate different blasting configurations according to real rock characteristics.

The different functionalities of the software are distributed in a work area, modules, tools, and status bar. In the projects section, the user has at his disposal tools for the creation of projects (or clients) and blasting, and a whole package of options to control the general options of the software. RIOBLAST is composed of different modules, as presented in Figure 17. Specifically:

- **Terrain (a):** module used to create and edit a terrain or import actual surveying data from scanning, laser, or UAV. It allows georeferencing of the created or imported terrain and the importation of external satellite maps of the mine to obtain a better visualisation of the blast ubication.
- **Blast geometry (b):** this module allows the user to create (by single, rows, areas, or pattern), import, and edit boreholes on the terrain and to load them with different types of explosives along the hole. A review of the designed blast can be visualised, exported, and modified in a resume table.
- **Timing (c):** simulation of timing/initiating sequence using non-electric systems to review and analyse the maximum instantaneous charge (MIC) on a timing sequence histogram and to visualise the timing isolines.
- **Vibration (d):** module that allows the user to incorporate an attenuation law in the database, draw peak particle velocity (PPV) isolines, and find specific distance vs PPV value range on the map. From it, the users can build/analyse their own attenuation law and simulate the wavefront and the seed wave.
- **Fly rocks (e):** calculation and representation of the fly rock safety range by taking three different methods: face burst, cratering, and rifling. Isolines incorporated on maps for personnel and equipment safety.
- **Fragmentation (f):** in this module, the user can define rock properties and assign them to a fully customisable rock area on the terrain. Based on this, the user can simulate the fragmentation results from the blast design generated. The results are represented in a fragmentation curve and can be exported to a table.
- **Advanced function – damage estimation (g, h):** the damage estimation is based on near-field vibration models, such as that of Holmberg and Persson (1978) is available from RIOBLAST. In addition, energy concentrations can be displayed as a function of powder factor or specific energy. This tool allows the identification of areas where there is an excess or lack of energy, making it possible to adjust the blasting design.

Figure 17. RIOBLAST modules: a) Terrain, b) Blast geometry, c) Timing, d) Vibrations, e) Fly rocks, f) Fragmentation, g) Near filed damage estimation, h) Energy distribution, i) Dilution, j) Reporting

5.1.2.1.1.3 X-Truck

It is the new generation of MAXAM’s fully digitalised Mobile Sensitising Unit (MSU). X-Truck integration with MAXAM digital environment via Blast Center allows an accurate execution of the designed loading plans at the bench. Additionally, the actual as-loaded data is remotely reported in real time. This loading system allows the variability of the explosive density in the column charge of the borehole adjusting it to the rock mass characteristics. Consequently, the use of the explosive can be optimised, reducing energy losses and powder factor, and allowing pattern expansion. The blast pattern, previously designed in RIOBLAST, is imported directly into the programmable logic controllers (PLC) of the MSU. Then, the user can directly select the boreholes to be loaded from the design of the blast. The loading plan, which contains the information of the different sections is also included in the design. The MSU and charging operations are shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18. MSU used in Valdilecha-CEMEX pilot site

5.1.2.1.1.4 X-Logger

A secure, efficient, and user-friendly portable device application to collect, verify, and update drilling and blasting data at the bench. X-Logger facilitates digitalising vital information for a sustainable blasting optimisation program. When using X-Logger, all the information is transferred in real time to Blast Center, including new boreholes not contained in the original blast plan. The system allows for multiple devices to operate simultaneously, including off-line mode communications.

Figure 19. X-Logger interface

5.1.2.1.1.5 QA/QC at Valdilecha-CEMEX pilot site

The drilling and blasting tests conducted at the Valdilecha-CEMEX pilot site include systematic quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) processes. All relevant data, i.e. that impact the blasting results, is collected and digitalised on the field. Figure 20 sketches the different tasks carried out during the blasting campaign regarding QA/QC.

Figure 20. Tasks to be carried out for a QA/QC analysis

5.1.2.1.2 Innovative explosive – RIOFLEX QY Smart System

RIOFLEX is a non-aluminised, highly energy bulk water gel explosive. A fit-for-purpose explosive in both non-reactive and reactive ground conditions, with a wide range of adjustable densities and excellent water resistance for use in wet and dry blastholes, open pits, and underground metal mines. It consists of a base oxidant matrix, a sensitizer and a cross linker, capable of being blended with ANFO. This flexible explosive can be manufactured with either dense or porous ammonium nitrate, which increases its manufacturing capabilities.

This highly flexible energy (HFE) water gel can be broadly grouped into three main families of sensitising processes: chemical and mechanical gassing and physical sensitising with micro-balloons. As a combination of special energetic run materials and high-density flexibility, this explosive can deliver tailored performance in a wide range of rock types and conditions. It allows not only significant improvements on rock fragmentation and heave, which can positively impact downstream operations, but also drill pattern expansions without impacting blast results and load and haul rates.

Once the HFE water gel is sensitised, the density distribution is fixed by the cross-linking process and will not drift through the influence of the environment. This process makes the product resistant to water and renders it impervious to the ingress of aggregate stemming. The stemming control is crucial to quality fragmentation, better confinement of the gasses and energy, and the control of ground vibration generated by blasting.

Figure 21 shows the density distribution of the HFE water gel along the borehole charge in comparison with a standard emulsion with an average density of 1,150 kg/m³. In this example, the energy distribution for the same in-hole density (or product quantity) is much better with the HFE water gel, yielding higher densities at the bottom and lower at the top. This distribution increases the available energy at the bottom of the hole, allowing the explosive to deliver more energy in this rock zone.

Figure 21. Flexible density distribution of the HFE watergel in comparison with a standard emulsion

5.1.2.2 Impact on energy efficiency

Depending on the recipe, a direct powder factor reduction (by density reduction or pattern expansion) between 5% and 15% could be applied to operations where the bulk emulsion is used without affecting blasting results in terms of fragmentation, loading rate, and comminution processes. In comparison to operations where ANFO is used, the reduction in powder factor could be between 5% and 10%.

Depending on the recipe, in addition to or instead of reducing the powder factor, the blast could be designed and loaded looking for a target fragmentation, loading rate, and comminution value, so improvements in the downstream operations could be achieved in terms of productivity and energy reductions. In quarries, a potential reduction of 10-20% of fine material could be achieved. Additionally, a potential reduction of 15-20% of coarse material could be expected, providing a more uniform fragmentation. Consequently, gross estimations indicate potential energy reductions in loading of 5-10% and 2-5% in crushing.

5.1.2.3 Other impacts

5.1.2.3.1 Productivity

MAXAM's X-Energy solutions allow customised designs for each blast, knowing how much explosive, initiation systems and stemming material is needed per blast. Design and actual data are collected (both geometrical blast parameters and explosive consumption) and stored in the cloud, making it possible to access fast analysis and automatic. Additionally, vibration measurements and the corresponding analysis can be included. All these contribute to a more efficient blasting tasks execution.

The X-Truck allows charging directly from the design, saving time and accurately estimating the amount of explosives consumed. In addition, customised designs according to the rock and the geometrical characteristics of the blasts can be carried out by varying the explosive density, optimising the volume of explosive to be used.

5.1.2.3.2 Safety

Safer working conditions can be achieved. The customised designs according to the rock and the geometrical characteristics of the blasts contribute to optimal blasting results, minimising rock projections and better controlling bench wall and vibration.

Additionally, it limits manual explosive loading since it is pumped from the truck.

5.1.2.3.3 Environment

The instantaneous crosslinker capability of the explosive minimises the migration of the explosive through cracks, and the possible dissolution of it in nearby water bodies, i.e. explosive leakage and water pollution is reduced.

5.1.2.3.4 Social acceptance

A better control of all parameters within the blast and the increase of safety conditions contribute to enhancing the perception of these processes.

A higher control of vibration can also be achieved through the right timing of the holes by using electronic detonators.

5.1.2.4 Limitations and future work

Limitations in terms of explosive supply and truck availability are related to the distance of the quarry from the factory and national regulations that constrain the circulation timing of the unit through public roads.

5.2 Material handling

5.2.1 Mobile crusher – Metso

Table 7. Summary Metso

Key information	Description
DEQ partner	Metso
Name of the technology	Lokotrack LT1213SE pilot machine
Type	Machinery, mobile crusher
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 4 (aiming to reach TRL 7 by the end of the project)
Installed power	Nominal 250 kW, maximum 315 kW
Energy efficiency improvement	15% fuel consumption reduction (expected) compared to the current commercial version of the machine

5.2.1.1 Description

Metso's contribution to the DEQ project is the implementation of a series-hybrid electric powertrain to a mobile, track-mounted impact crusher (Figure 22). The technology does not affect the crushing itself, i.e. the crusher, its motor, and power transmission from the motor to the crusher axle remain the same. However, the hybrid powertrain is expected to achieve higher overall energy efficiency from diesel fuel or an external source to the crusher motor. An increase in available power, and therefore productivity, is also achieved through the inclusion of a high-power Li-ion battery.

Figure 22. Lokotrack LT1213SE pilot machine technology in Metso Tampere factory workshop

Overall efficiency is improved through an intelligent control system. This balances the load between the onboard genset and battery to achieve the best possible operating points for the genset while reducing transient effects experienced by the internal combustion engine, further reducing consumption and emissions. Onboard power generation is required in these machines as they are often utilised in remote areas without access to external energy sources such as the electric grid. Therefore, it is important to optimise their use until greener onboard energy sources, e.g. biofuels and hydrogen, become more accessible. Electrification and hybridisation of the powertrain is a step in this direction as well, as the powertrain is energy-source agnostic, i.e. it can be powered by any kind of rotating machine regardless of the fuel it uses.

5.2.1.2 Impact on energy efficiency

With a hybrid powertrain, the machine is expected to reduce fuel consumption by 15% on average. With higher availability and stability of power, the crusher is expected to work more efficiently, reducing specific energy consumption. However, these results are still estimations and will be validated as soon as practical tests are performed with the machine.

5.2.1.3 Other impacts

5.2.1.3.1 Productivity

The productivity of the machine is expected to increase thanks to the enhanced stability of the crusher due to the higher availability of energy and instantaneous power from the powertrain.

5.2.1.3.2 Safety

The safety of the machine is improved via reduced noise (noise encapsulation, lower diesel engine speeds).

5.2.1.3.3 Environment

The environmental impact of the machine is limited by reducing its noise and GHG emissions. GHG emissions are reduced by smoother engine operations (less NOx and PM as the engine experiences fewer transients) and by reduced fuel

consumption. The developed powertrain is “prime mover agnostic”, i.e. it can be equipped with any machine capable of producing DC current regardless of the original source of the energy, enabling zero-emission operations in the future by, for example, using sources such as hydrogen ICE, or fuel cell.

5.2.1.3.4 Social acceptance

The development of this machine can contribute to greater social acceptance of the quarrying operation by reducing the environmental impact of the crusher.

5.2.1.4 Limitations and future work

The results presented in this document correspond to the estimations based on system simulations at Metso Factory in Tampere, Finland. Physical tests to validate the simulation results at the Fenouillet-VICAT site are to be performed in the upcoming months.

5.2.2 Loading and hauling – Abaut

Table 8. Summary Abaut

Key information	Description
DEQ partner	Abaut
Name of the technology	Abaut
Type	Hardware and software for monitoring mobile heavy machinery
Technology Readiness Level	Production and productivity: TRL 9 Fleet efficiency: TRL 8 Mine organization & machinery availability: TRL 7 Idle times & inefficiencies: TRL 7 Communication and reporting: TRL 8
Installed power	Low-consumption hardware connected to the power supply in the cabin of the machine via its 12V connector
Energy efficiency improvement	5-10% specific fuel consumption reduction (expected) in mobile machinery

5.2.2.1 Description

Abaut’s technology is based on the hardware and software developed by the company for monitoring the mobile heavy machinery.

The monitoring hardware is a tool that provides insight into the operation and interoperability of different types of machines, e.g. drill rig, excavator, trucks, etc., brands and models, with the possibility of including older machines (retrofit). To gather mining process data, sensors and cameras are installed on every mobile mining equipment that is involved in the production process from overburden removal and drilling towards unloading at a crusher. Depending on the infrastructure of the mining operation, additional information along the supply chain may be included, e.g. crusher energy consumption.

Monitoring machine activity can yield results such as identifying potential optimisation opportunities for individual subtasks, statistical analyses of changes in normal operation and the significance of these differences, and weighting the importance of specific measures on the overall process.

The raw data is captured second-wise, and the picture data is every five seconds. The data is transmitted every 10 minutes through a VPN tunnel in near real-time using terrestrial or 3G/4G connectivity, accessed via M2M SIM cards until it is received, synchronised, and stored in the backend system. Additionally, if desired, it is possible to have the position of the machine in real-time by sending the data captured every second.

Regarding the different software modules and the hardware available, it is possible to integrate the features “in-demand”. The basis of the system relies on the raw data collected by the sensor module. Once the sensor is connected, it transmits the information needed for the different software modules.

The information and modules can work independently or in combination to provide the most reliable information possible.

5.2.2.1.1 Hardware component

About’s monitoring system is based on its own self-developed and patented hardware. The hardware consists of a sensor unit, its power supply, and an antenna. If needed, the sensor unit can include a camera installed in the cabin of the mobile machinery. The sensor box for data collection includes GNSS, accelerometer, gyroscope, thermometer, and barometer.

5.2.2.1.2 Software component

About’s expert system works in five different software modules accessible at About’s platform and also through the frontend and the REST API in the DEQ’s IQS developed by AKKODIS. These modules are Production and productivity, Fleet efficiency, Mine organization & machinery availability, Idle times & inefficiencies, and Communication and reporting (each module is described below in the following subsections).

5.2.2.1.2.1 *Production and productivity*

This module provides all the information related to the production, mass flow and productivity of the machines in operation. The traceability of the material allows further analysis considering the geological rock quality and material behaviour, together with their impact on the other subsequent mining processes and tasks.

5.2.2.1.2.2 *Fleet efficiency*

In this module, it is possible to observe the different activities carried out at the fleet level and the interconnections between the different machines. To increase the performance of the fleet, it is possible to set up different dashboards and analytics. This powerful tool improves the performance, reducing the energy consumption and the environmental impact of the activities. Activities such as the loading and unloading time are reported according to their time and locations and, in addition, the interaction between the different machinery.

5.2.2.1.2.3 *Mine organization & machinery utilization*

It includes functionalities to export data regarding working hours, the starting of the operations, and the number of machines per shift, among others. The integrated fleet management system and analytics include not only the availability of the machines but are also connected to the machine utilisation as well as the production and daily plan.

5.2.2.1.2.4 *Idle times & inefficiencies*

In this module, it is possible to analyse the different idle times in the mine and sort them by machinery, location, or duration. In addition, it is possible to observe and visualize the different bottlenecks of operations at the map application (Figure 23).

5.2.2.1.2.5 *Communication and reporting*

This module is in charge of transferring the information to the reporting system (e.g. SAP) of the site and bringing the results of About’s expert system to the IQS of DEQ.

Figure 23. Abaut's system map application in Valdilecha-CEMEX

5.2.2.2 Impact on energy efficiency

A direct improvement is related to the decrease in idle times, which is directly related to fuel consumption and working hours and to the optimisation of the haulage routes. This improvement can vary from quarry to quarry, but this optimisation can lead to an estimated value, depending on the size of the operation and how the machinery operates, of 5-10% cost reduction regarding fuel consumption.

Secondary impacts are related to fleet efficiency. Thanks to the monitoring tool, fleet capabilities can be maximised. For example, if the cycle times allow, a second or third truck can be used together with one excavator, maintenance or program stops can be planned if production is going according to plan, etc.

In addition, better machinery availability and a reduction of idle times can decrease maintenance costs and energy consumption.

5.2.2.3 Other impacts

5.2.2.3.1 Productivity

The system allows for the enhancement of the machinery fleet and its productivity, which is directly related to the five modules of the tool.

5.2.2.3.2 Safety

The installation of a camera with the hardware in the mobile machinery allows capabilities directly related to safety, specifically the detection of people near the machinery. Such a system has been tested to recognise individuals around the machinery and integrate the results into a dynamic map application called the "Risk Map Application." This application provides insights into the location, timestamp, speed, and path of the machinery, helping to ensure compliance with health and safety (H&S) protocols.

5.2.2.3.3 Environment

A reduction in idle times leads directly to a reduction in fuel consumption. In addition, the emissions are reduced. Another important factor is the road status and the analysis of the velocities. An enhancement of the hauling routes through better road maintenance, in combination with the analysis of the velocities, could cause a decrease in the dust generated.

5.2.2.3.4 Social acceptance

Thanks to the integration of the relevant fleet KPIs and the integration of different types of imagery, e.g., drone images or 360-degree imagery, transparency can be enhanced by showing the relevant stakeholders how the activities are carried out place or the status of the remediation plans, among others.

5.2.2.4 Limitations and future work

Further applications need to be studied and correlated with market needs. Some of the future work can focus on the development of new tools and applications for the monitoring system. Different AI-ML algorithm tools could be developed to integrate new KPIs coming from the camera module. In addition, the integration of more machinery types, e.g. graders, bulldozers, etc., could represent an opportunity for further operational improvements.

5.2.3 Loading and hauling – DH&P

Table 9. Summary DH&P

Key information	Description
DEQ partner	DOHMEN, HERZOG & Partner GmbH – DH&P
Name of the technology	AutoPLAN
Type	Hardware and software for monitoring mobile heavy machinery
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 6
Installed power	Low-consumption hardware connected to the power supply in the cabin of the machine via its 12V connector (a battery is included)
Energy efficiency improvement	Fuel consumption reduction to be determined

5.2.3.1 Description

DH&P’s development within the DEQ project includes its expert system AutoPLAN. The solution is based on an OEM-independent data logger installed on a mixed quarry fleet capable of transmitting the CAN bus raw data. The logger can be installed in all the essential mobile machinery all essential for the quarry, i.e. haul trucks, excavators, wheel loaders, and standard four axle road trucks. The data is then integrated into the system and combined with additional data, e.g. surveying or manual documentation, for the calculation of meaningful KPIs to be used by the quarry staff to understand the process and identify areas for improvement.

The aim is to contribute to optimising fuel consumption in mobile machinery and consequently reducing CO₂ emissions. Likewise, the insight gained during operation is expected to improve the machines’ utilisation, quarry road conditions, and downtime. Therefore, the logger also records and transmits the machines’ positions. Figure 24 shows how the exact geolocation of a machine can be displayed on AutoPLAN, allowing a better understating and analysis of the incoming raw data.

Figure 24. AutoPLAN mapping tool with the drive tracks displayed for one day

DH&P's data logger and system have been implemented at the Mammendorf-CSI pilot site. It is tested for reliability and durability in the harsh quarry environment and for general feasibility for the collection of the required data. The loggers are installed to implement non-invasive data recording from the onboard CAN bus network on different machine types, all essential for the quarry operation, such as dump trucks, excavators, wheel loaders and standard four-axle road trucks. The data availability from the only partially standardised OEM CAN BUS network of each machine type is analysed during the machine's regular quarry operation. The CAN BUS data and the machines position are recorded by the logger and transmitted via mobile network to the data cloud. Here the raw data is managed using the multifunctional expert system AutoPLAN.

5.2.3.2 Impact on energy efficiency

The analysis of CAN bus data from the machines used in the quarry for extraction, loading and hauling can be used in many ways to optimise energy consumption. The most obvious use of the data is the evaluation of driving movements and transport distances. This allows optimisations to be carried out in route guidance, ramp gradients, and road conditions. In addition, possible mismatches between loading and hauling machines, which result in longer loading cycles, can be detected. Next to these analysis tools relating to the operational process, incorrect machine handling by the operator can also be detected and optimised through training.

At the company level, great synergy effects can be achieved in terms of reporting by using this system. Currently, fuel consumption is largely recorded manually. The system enables automated, manufacturer-independent reporting of the quarrying process, which saves personnel costs for compiling fuel consumption data as well as permanent manual documentation. Fuel consumption can be displayed per machine, for selected machines, or for the entire quarry. If several quarries are integrated into the system, the reporting can even upscale the cost savings for reporting to all integrated quarries.

Reporting on energy efficiency and CO₂ emissions is becoming increasingly critical to satisfy stakeholders' scrutiny. In this context, tools like DH&P's AutoPLAN expert system are especially important for transparent and cost-effective reporting.

5.2.3.3 Other impacts

5.2.3.3.1 Productivity

The system allows the enhancement of the machinery fleet and its productivity.

5.2.3.3.2 Safety

The analysis of the mobile equipment's driving movements can also be used to display areas with particularly high traffic volumes. Potential hazards can be pointed out by, for example, setting up warning signs, contributing to their mitigation.

5.2.3.3.3 Environment

Positive effects on the environment are directly linked to the described effects on the possibilities of reduced energy consumption.

5.2.3.3.4 Social acceptance

DH&P's system contributes to enhancing transparency through the integration of mobile machinery data and reporting tools, which facilitates greater social acceptance.

5.2.3.4 Limitations and future work

Currently, DH&P is focused on the improvement and validation of the KPIs and the integration of further quarry machinery. At the same time, additional sensors are being installed and tested to gain a full-on picture of the quarry workflow.

5.3 Processing

5.3.1 Plant optimisation – Arco

Table 10. Summary Arco

Key information	Description
DEQ partner	Arco Electrónica S.A.
Name of the technology	Arco Mineral Platinum Arco Monitor Weighing systems
Type	Sensors
Technology Readiness Level	Arco Mineral Platinum: TRL 8 (aiming to reach TRL 9 by the end of the project) Weighing system: TRL 5 (aiming to reach TRL 9 by the end of the project)
Installed power	Low-consumption sensors (60-144 W)
Energy efficiency improvement	To be determined

5.3.1.1 Description

In a quarry, sensor parameters and variables are used to monitor and control processes related to the extraction and handling of materials. At the plant, the supervision of these sensors can be done through a SCADA system (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) or an industrial automation system. These systems collect data from sensors in real-time, allowing operators to monitor key variables, receive alarms, and make adjustments or take action as needed. In addition, the data collected by the sensors can also be used for further analysis, reporting, and optimisation of processes in a quarry.

Arco’s work in the DEQ project focuses on further developing the SCADA systems of the pilot sites by implementing their Arco Mineral Platinum aggregate plant control software and installing weighing systems.

Specifically, at the Pioltello-HOLCIM and Fenouillet-VICAT pilot sites, one and two weighing systems have been installed, respectively. In the case of Alenquer-CIMPOR, Arco has provided eight weighing systems, two metal detectors, and the supervision of the existing sensors in the pilot plant.

5.3.1.1.1 Software component: Arco Mineral Platinum and Arco Monitor

The Arco Mineral Platinum software (Figure 25) supports aggregates plants in achieving greater production control, reducing production costs, and improving energy efficiency. To do this, different sensors, specifically the DEQ project weighing systems, are installed at the pilot sites’ plants. The software collects and centralises this data and can also transmit it to the IQS.

Figure 25. Arco Mineral Platinum software – SCADA at the Alenquer-CIMPOR pilot site

Complementary, the Arco Monitor (Figure 26) software is a program for the centralised configuration and taring of up to 10 integrated weighing from an industrial or portable PC unit. Through this platform, it is possible to read and export weights to other formats, e.g. XLS, DBF, and TXT, among many other functions.

Figure 26. Arco Monitor software

5.3.1.1.2 Hardware component: weighing systems

The implementation of weighing systems in quarries has several key objectives that contribute to improving the efficiency and control of operations and production. Regarding the implementation of these weighing systems within the project (Figure 27), we can list some specific sub-objectives.

- **Inventory control:** accurate real-time measuring of the weight of the material extracted, transported, and stored facilitates production planning and delivery scheduling, avoiding disruption due to material shortages.
- **Accurate billing:** accurate measurement ensures fair and transparent billing.
- **Efficiency optimisation:** monitoring the performance and efficiency of operations allows the identification of areas for improvement. Crushers' feed rates and the flow of material on the conveyors can be adjusted to maximise production.
- **Quality control:** measuring the weight of the material at different stages of the process allows quality standards verification. If deviations are detected, corrective measures can be taken to ensure the quality of the products.

Figure 27. Arco's weighing system

Weighing systems are based on principles such as tensile force, pressure load, and speed measurement to calculate the weight of materials in real-time. Arco manufactures on demand a special weighing trough adapted to the customer's conveyor belt and production.

These systems use a variety of advanced sensors and technologies to achieve accurate and reliable measurements. Some of these technologies include load cells, pressure sensors, speed sensors, and automatic sampling systems. These devices

are integrated with data processing algorithms to provide accurate and real-time measurements. Within DEQ, Arco has implemented a speed/turn meter based on an encoder (Figure 28). It provides detailed and exact measurements in terms of angular position or angular velocity, as well as real-time feedback on motor speed or rotation.

Figure 28. Speed meter – Encoder

5.3.1.2 Impact on energy efficiency

With plant automation, it is possible to optimise the operating time of the machines. In this way, a start/stop is applied to the machines so that they remain on standby and are only in operation when necessary. This translates into a great reduction in energy consumption.

With the installation of weighing systems, the speed of the machines that directly affect the belt can be regulated, adjusting production. This can reduce consumption since the machines will work only for the desired production.

Finally, machine breakdowns can be avoided and, in consequence, their useful life can be extended.

5.3.1.3 Other impacts

5.3.1.3.1 Productivity

As mentioned, these systems allow greater control of machinery productivity. They provide a global vision of all processes in real-time from a central station. This facilitates monitoring multiple areas of the quarry, such as crushers, conveyors, stockpiles, etc. The centralised monitoring provides proper insight for well-informed decision-making. Problems or anomalies in the operation can be rapidly identified, and all corrective measures can be implemented.

5.3.1.3.2 Safety

The remote control of devices and processes at the plant allows adjustments and configurations to be made without the need for physical intervention on the site. This reduces workers' exposure to hazards, thus improving safety conditions in the operations.

5.3.1.3.3 Environment

Improving the energy efficiency of the plant leads to a reduction in the emissions associated with electricity consumption.

5.3.2 Plant optimisation – Ma-estro

Table 11. Summary Ma-estro

Key information	Description
DEQ partner	Ma-estro
Name of the technology	Q-Volumetric Q-Vision Q-Production
Type	Sensors & Cloud Software
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 9
Installed power	Low-consumption sensors (40-55 W)
Energy efficiency improvement	Up to 15% specific energy consumption reduction at the plant (expected)

5.3.2.1 Description

As part of the DEQ project to promote energy efficiency and industrial optimisation, Ma-estro has been actively involved in implementing advanced technologies for plant optimisation and automation. This section provides a detailed description of the technology utilised by Ma-estro on the sites where interventions are conducted, particularly at the Pioltello-HOLCIM pilot site (see Figure 29).

Figure 29. Ma-estro’s sensors deployment at the Pioltello-HOLCIM pilot site

5.3.2.1.1 Hardware component

The hardware component encompasses a range of sensors tailored to the specific requirements of each plant and the final client's needs. Solutions for volumetric calculations, granulometric control sensors, and pressure or absorption control

sensors for various machinery involved in the production process are essential. The specific hardware components are described in the following subsections.

5.3.2.1.2 Volumetric calculation solutions: Q-Volumetric

The technology for volumetric calculation solutions typically involves the integration of high-precision sensors capable of accurately measuring volumes of materials processed within the plant. These sensors may include ultrasonic sensors, laser-based measurement systems, or electromagnetic flow meters, depending on the application requirements and environmental conditions. Q-Volumetric consists of an encoder and a flow sensor, which is the Bulkscan® sensor. The flow sensor is based on non-contact time-of-flight technology, and it measures the volume flow of bulk materials on conveyor belts. In particular, the system generates a reliable volume flow signal based on the laser's time of flight and the belt speed, thanks to multi-echo technology. The light source is an Infrared of 905 nm of wavelength.

5.3.2.1.3 Granulometric control sensors: Q-Vision

Granulometric control sensors play a crucial role in ensuring the consistency and quality of the final product. Ma-estro employs advanced granulometric control sensors, such as an AI-based image control system, to monitor particle size distribution within the production process. These sensors provide real-time data, enabling prompt adjustments to optimise product quality and efficiency. In the Q-Vision system there is only one camera: specifically, it is a Computar M1614-MP2. Its vision lenses are engineered for maximum performance in close-up applications required in factory automation, robotics, and image processing areas.

The resolution limit of the camera depends, in addition to its technical characteristics, on the height at which it is installed, as well as the customer's needs and spending budget.

The Q-Vision, by applying artificial intelligence, is able to create an outline around each individual grain and stone on the conveyor belt of a plant. It then calculates the largest diameter of each grain to identify a series of virtual sieves based on the grain sizes present. Based on the percentage of material retained on each sieve level, the system generates the fineness modulus. This system is useful when used before and after a crusher, as done in the Pioltello pilot site, to understand if the crusher is operating as desired and if the desired level of crushing is being achieved. It can also be applied on the exit belts carrying the final product to check its quality.

In the case of the Pioltello plant, the resolution at the grain size level has a lower limit of 6 mm.

5.3.2.1.4 Pressure or absorption control sensors

Pressure and absorption control sensors are utilised to monitor and regulate the performance of various machinery involved in the production process. Ma-estro integrates sophisticated pressure sensors and absorption meters to precisely measure and control pressure levels and material absorption rates, ensuring optimal operational conditions and energy efficiency.

Pressure sensors collect data from water cyclones, and thanks to their analysis, it is possible to verify the machines' working performance. The pressure analysis is helpful in understanding if the water cyclones are in optimal loading conditions or if they work with a small amount of loaded material. Through these data, it is possible to work towards decreasing water consumption and increasing efficiency.

Each hydrocyclone model has its own ideal processing pressure, and any variation in this indicates a change within the system.

According to Ma-estro's experience in the quarrying sector and considering the hydrocyclone models present at the Pioltello site, the pressure sensor indicates the presence of sand when the water pressure decreases (approximately less than 0.6 bar). The more sediment there is, the less water pressure inside the machine, and the greater the likelihood of throwing out fine material along with the dirty water.

5.3.2.1.5 Software component: Q-Production

In addition to the hardware components, Ma-estro's technology framework incorporates advanced software solutions to facilitate data analysis, process optimisation, and automation. The software component involves the creation of a cloud-based portal that gathers and processes all collected data relevant to improving the plant's production process. The portal is accessible via credentials and can be viewed in real time, with data uploaded every five minutes on any mobile device, making information easily accessible and understandable.

5.3.2.2 Impact on energy efficiency

Past experiences have shown significant improvements in energy efficiency. For example, one of Ma-estro's projects, involving the revamping of a crushing plant, achieved a 10% increase in production within the manufacturing process, with energy savings per ton produced ranging from 4.2 kW/ton per hour to 3.5 kW/ton per hour. Plant downtime decreased by 5%. Thanks to plant optimisation, a 4% reduction in component consumption was also observed. All of this, of course, leads to increased workplace safety, remote machinery control, and controlled maintenance. The data collected from the installed sensors allow for setting an optimal range of machine operation within the plant, leading to real-time data control, energy efficiency, and data control on any mobile device through the web portal.

Specifically, in the DEQ project, Ma-estro collaborates with the Pioltello-HOLCIM and Fenouillet-VICAT pilot sites. At the Pioltello site, the initial phase of plant analysis has been completed, followed by the installation of necessary sensors for production control. The next step is to proceed with plant automation. However, this step requires a plant shutdown, and discussions with the pilot site partner are ongoing to determine the optimal timing for this.

At the Fenouillet pilot site, the primary phase of data collection is currently being carried out. This will enable detailed analysis and subsequent action planning.

Regarding energy efficiency improvements, tangible results have not yet been observed as they typically follow automation implementation. Nevertheless, the installed sensors provide valuable insights into the operational trends of certain machines. By understanding the optimal operating range, adjustments can be made gradually towards optimisation.

The installation of Ma-estro's systems allows for more consistent energy consumption over time, without positive or negative spikes associated with excessive or minimal work of specific machinery. By monitoring all plant machinery and ensuring optimal operation, minimum electricity consumption is guaranteed.

5.3.2.3 Other impacts

5.3.2.3.1 Productivity

Implementing Maestro's systems is expected to improve productivity significantly. However, the actual improvement will depend on the type of system and the starting situation. If the operation has little to no optimisation tools at the plants, productivity could increase by more than 15%. In other cases, improvements in the range of 10-12% can be expected, as in the Vezzola SPA case (one of the latest sites automated and monitored by Ma-estro).

5.3.2.3.2 Safety

The digitisation of plant data and the optimisation of production processes inevitably result in enhanced safety conditions for workers within crushing plants in quarries. This improvement is attributed to controlled machinery maintenance facilitated by regular alerts provided through Ma-estro's portal. As a result, there is reduced wear and fewer manual interventions required directly in the field.

Clear indications regarding the operating status of individual machines also allow the maintenance process to be managed more precisely, punctually and safely, having had the opportunity to plan it correctly.

5.3.2.3.3 Environment

Various improvements are observed in terms of environmental impact. Depending on the specific circumstances, at some sites, optimisation and control of the production process have reduced noise pollution from certain equipment. This reduction is a result of regular maintenance and the absence of wear on components that would otherwise contribute to higher noise levels.

Another significant improvement is the reduction in water consumption, achieved by controlling the pressure of machinery involved in the production process and regulating the quantity of materials on the conveyor belts that eventually feed into washing screens. Maintaining a consistent initial flow rate allows for better resource utilisation and reduces conveyor belt wear. Digitalising a plant leads to reduced wear and tear, fewer spare parts, and less waste.

Finally, digitalisation and automation of the process also facilitate reducing electricity consumption per ton produced, thus reducing the associated CO₂ emissions.

5.3.2.3.4 Social acceptance

Ma-estro’s solutions indirectly assist a quarry in achieving greater social acceptability. The reduction of energy waste is one of the strongest arguments, and Ma-estro contributes to improving the community’s perception by providing concrete numbers and real data.

5.3.2.4 Limitations and future work

Moving forward, the focus will be on advancing automation at the pilot sites to realise energy efficiency gains. Additionally, ongoing data analysis from the installed sensors will support decision-making processes to optimise machine usage and improve overall energy performance.

Future work at Ma-estro’s is strongly focused towards artificial intelligence. One of the next products that is in an advanced stage of development is called Q-Pilot. It is an artificial intelligence-based system designed to function as a unified solution integrating machinery and operators. It will be capable of assisting operators in making complex decisions, helping them better manage efficiency and maximise the plant’s potential while ensuring continuous production control at an optimal level.

5.3.3 Plant optimisation – Mintek

Table 12. Summary Mintek

Key information	Description
DEQ partner	Mintek
Name of the technology	Breakage and screening models, online particle size distribution (PSD) measurement, local crushing/screening interface (LCSI), and digital twins
Type	Digital twin
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 4 (aiming to reach TRL 5 by the end of the project)
Installed power	N/A
Energy efficiency improvement	No estimation available

5.3.3.1 Description

Mintek’s contribution to DEQ consist of the creation of a digital twin with crushing and screening interfaces. This includes the development of breakage and screening models, online particle size distribution (PSD) measurements, remote crushing and screening interface (RCSI), and local crushing and screening interface (LCSI). The measurements are taken at the

Pioltello-HOLCIM site by means of the Q-Vision sensors installed by Ma-estro (see section 5.3.2.1.3) and the weightmeters provided by Arco (see section 5.3.1).

The digital twin comprises a crushing-screening circuit. Its goal is to be used as a tool for plant optimisation through changes in certain operational parameters without interfering with the physical plant's production. The digital twin will consist of two Excel®-consoles with the IDEAS flowsheet simulator (Figure 30).

Specifically, Mintek will use this technology to simulate a section of the Pioltello site's flowsheet and act as an advisory tool for optimising this section of the plant. The current version of the digital twin features an Excel® interface used for model calibration and data analysis, as well as flowsheet simulation software used to simulate the crushing and screening circuit.

Mintek is also designing a local crushing and screening interface for the Pioltello site. The system design will include a measurement and data storage service, digital twin simulation service, digital twin calibration service, data connectors, calibration and simulation agents, and the user interface.

Though, in the DEQ project, this technology consists of a single digital twin model with its associated supporting features, it can be scaled up in future applications at these or other quarries. Mintek can incorporate more models and simulation units as long as there is sufficient calibration data and representative model equations.

Figure 30. IDEAS™ flowsheet model³

5.3.3.2 Connectivity

The digital twin service is cloud-based. Therefore, internet access for a computer connected to the plant’s programmable logic controller (PLC) is required. Likewise, the computer used by the quarry staff members to interact with the digital twin Service must have an internet connection. Both wired and wireless connections are suitable. Although optional, end users may access the system from mobile devices, e.g. tablets. These mobile devices require mobile (4G/5G) or Wi-Fi internet connection.

5.3.3.3 Impact on energy efficiency

³ PSD blocks display the PSD of components within the attached stream. They do not correspond to PSD instruments installed on the crushing circuit.

As mentioned previously, the digital twin service will be stored on a cloud-based platform. The only requirement at the quarry plant is an electronic device with internet connectivity capable of running the latest internet browsers. Therefore, there is no fixed energy consumption on-site associated with utilising this aspect of the digital twin technology.

The aim of this technology is to act as an advisory tool for the optimisation of the real-life process on which the digital twin is based. The key objective of this strategy is to optimise the product PSD from the crusher based on economic and environmental objectives. Part of the economic objective is to increase the production of the plant's most viable size fraction whilst limiting the production of the less valuable sizes. This could result in the plant meeting its production targets with fewer operating hours for the crusher and aid in the reduction of energy consumption.

Regardless, and since digital twin solutions are still in relative infancy compared to other technologies, there are no concrete references on the percentage of energy consumption reduction that can be achieved solely from the application of this technology for plant optimisation.

5.3.3.4 Other impacts

5.3.3.4.1 Productivity

Mintek aims to leverage this technology to advise changes to the plant's operating parameters, e.g., crusher feed throughput and closed-side setting, that will improve the economic value of products produced and allow more efficient energy usage.

5.3.3.4.2 Safety

The production of fines in quarries can be a health and safety hazard, as inhalation of these fines can result in lung diseases such as silicosis and asthma. This necessitates the wearing of personal protective equipment (PPE), such as dust masks, in these processing environments. Complementary to these measures, the digital twin is able to advise the plant personnel on crusher operating parameters that could reduce the production of these fines and help reduce the associated health risks.

5.3.3.4.3 Environment

As mentioned previously, the digital twin technology has the potential to aid in the reduction of fine production. Depending on the particular case, this would result in less air pollution.

5.3.3.5 Limitations and future work

The effectiveness of this technology as an advisory tool for the optimisation of the simulated process is highly dependent on the accuracy of the data used during its calibration and validation. There is also a need to ensure that the data used is representative of the full range of operation of the physical process.

Future work will seek to expand this technology to other sections of the typical quarry flowsheet and other chemical or physical processes.

5.4 External transport

As mentioned in section 3, this stage in the quarrying value chain is generally carried out by third parties thus, it is not under the scope of the operation management. For this reason, the DEQ project has focused on the previous unit processes.

Regardless, Abaut's technology (see section 5.2.2) has been installed in a truck of one external transporter at the Alenquer-CIMPOR site. The information gathered, though confidential, provides insight into the shipment routes, the area of influence of the pilot site, and environmental aspects regarding the transport of aggregates.

Nevertheless, for energy efficiency considerations, this phase is out of the scope of the DEQ project.

5.5 Supporting technologies and cross-sectional analysis

5.5.1 Drill-to-mill – UPM-M & MAXAM

Table 13. Summary UPM-M & MAXAM

Key information	Description
DEQ partners	Polytechnic University of Madrid – Mining (UPM-M) MAXAM
Name of the technology	Drill-to-mill analysis
Type	Supporting technologies and data analysis
Technology Readiness Level	MWD to guide quarry blasting: TRL 5 (aiming to reach TRL 7 by the end of the project) Prediction of rock mass damage from blasting by using the full-field solution: TRL 3 (aiming to reach TRL 6) Drill-to-mill algorithms for quarrying: TRL 5 (aiming to reach TRL 7)
Installed power	N/A
Energy efficiency improvement	To be determined

5.5.1.1 Description

The efficiency and effectiveness of blasting techniques have a direct impact on the overall productivity, cost-effectiveness, and safety of mining operations. One fundamental goal of blasting is to achieve the desired fragmentation size distribution with the proper balance between coarse and fine material. This balance directly affects the productivity of the excavation equipment, cycle times of material hauling, and the overall plant efficiency in terms of material throughput and power requirements during subsequent crushing and grinding processes.

In this context, UPM-M and MAXAM develop a drill-to-mill methodology to be applied at Valdilecha-CEMEX pilot site, to analyse the relation between key parameters of different processes along the value chain. The methodology is based on data gathered along different processes, as shown in Figure 31. Several expert systems described in this report provide data for this analysis, specifically:

- Measurement while drilling (MWD) data provided by Sandvik (see section 5.1.1)
- Blasting data provided by MAXAM (see section 5.1.2)
- Loading rates provided by About (see section 5.2.2)

The processing energy consumption is provided by Valdilecha-CEMEX pilot site.

Figure 31. Data collected at different stages for drill-to-mill analysis

Additionally, UPM-M deploys a series of solutions to generate key data that is not provided by other expert systems. These solutions are described below.

5.5.1.1.1 Rock mass classification based on machine learning techniques

Based on the MWD data provided by Sandvik, machine learning algorithms have been developed for the geomechanical and structural rock mass classification. It is expected that this classification allows adapting the blast design and explosive charging in quarries, achieving a more efficient and safer use of the explosives.

5.5.1.1.2 Full-field solution

The full-field solution (FFS) of the seismic radiation from a blasthole is refined using a source function consistent with the shock physics on the detonation shock/rock interface and taking into account the influence of the free face.

Through this method, it should be possible to predict vibrations in the near field for damage mapping around boreholes and further backbreak prediction. This translates into the improvement of safety and better working conditions due to the reduction of damage in the remaining rock mass (high wall).

5.5.1.1.3 Drill-to-mill algorithms

The drill-to-mill methodology includes developing proper algorithms to link all key parameters in the different stages: rock features, blasting design, and muckpile properties. This is expected to improve the overall mining-processing cycles and the plant's performance.

An accurate point cloud is the base for calculating the actual drilling pattern and volume of broken rock. If the information is available before drilling, a more uniform explosive distribution will be possible thanks to an accurate knowledge of the burden and spacing of each hole. The goal is to achieve a more uniform fragmentation and a safer blast by limiting flyrock.

Likewise, the post-flight point cloud provides the data to calculate the muckpile profile (material range) and rock fragmentation from 3D photogrammetric models.

For the case of Valdilecha-CEMEX and considering a constant amount of natural fines (i.e. clay), the objectives are to increase the working time of the primary circuit, decrease the fraction bypassing the crusher, increase the pre-stock fraction, and decrease the fraction of reject (0-40 mm).

5.5.1.2 Impact on energy efficiency

The drill-to-mill methodology aims to improve the overall efficiency of the quarrying operation, which includes improvements in the energy consumed at the different stages by the machinery involved, i.e. excavators, by facilitating loading tasks and plant performance due to enhanced fragmentation. However, the actual impact on energy consumption will be determined once the tests and analysis conclude.

5.5.1.3 Other impacts

5.5.1.3.1 Productivity

The goal of the methodology is to improve efficiency and productivity by conducting an integrated analysis across unit processes.

5.5.1.3.2 Safety

The application of the drill-to-mill concept leads to safer working conditions by limiting flyrock during the blast and by reducing the damage in the remaining rock mass.

5.5.1.3.3 Environment

The main contribution to environmental impact mitigation comes from the improvements in energy efficiency and the associated GHG emissions reduction. Additionally, enhanced blasting and fragmentation can reduce the fines produced and consequently, the dust emissions.

5.5.1.4 Limitations and future work

The focus of UPM-M and MAXAM is now on collecting sufficient operational data of all the involved processes to develop and test the drill-to-mill algorithms.

5.5.2 Machine learning and fuel consumption analysis – MUL

Table 14. Summary MUL

Key information	Description
DEQ partner	Montanuniversität Leoben (MUL)
Name of the technology	N/A
Type	Data analysis
Technology Readiness Level	N/A
Installed power	N/A
Energy efficiency improvement	To be determined

5.5.2.1 Description

Part of MUL’s work within the DEQ project focuses on identifying potential areas for optimisation in the quarry workflow. Considering that material handling and comminution are the unit processes that represent the largest share of energy consumption in mining operations (Awuah-Offei 2016; Holmberg et al. 2017), improvements in haul truck fuel consumption can have a significant impact on quarries’ overall energy efficiency.

The deployment of artificial intelligence (AI) across the mining industry brings evident benefits throughout the mining lifecycle, from initial exploration to market price monitoring. AI technologies can decrease equipment downtime, streamline operations, enhance energy efficiency, optimise logistics, and significantly reduce costs. These improvements can subsequently elevate the profitability of mining enterprises.

In this context, the implementation of Bayesian models is particularly noteworthy. Bayesian networks (BNs) have the potential to uncover hidden relationships between the variables measured through the installed sensors on the mobile fleet (see sections 5.2.2 and 5.2.3). Furthermore, BNs facilitate the prediction of outcomes for any model variable, manage uncertainty propagation, and aid in knowledge generation, particularly in scenarios where the task is too complex or simply unknown for a human expert. Due to their foundation in graph theory, these networks are especially effective for graphical interpretation via digital interfaces, as illustrated in the example of Figure 32.

Figure 32. Example of an unsupervised Bayesian network using node force mapping for one week of sensor analysis focused on the CAT 775G Dump Truck at the Mammendorf-CSI pilot site⁴

The use of BNs in the DEQ project proves invaluable for causal reasoning, enabling the reverse engineering of effects from known causes. For example, this methodology allows for the assessment of risks associated with operational inefficiencies, such as areas with excessive idle times, disrupted drive cycles characterised by frequent braking and acceleration, or work situations with high energy consumption. Furthermore, BNs enable the monitoring of variables that significantly influence the development of these adverse conditions. By employing information theory, the interactions between network variables—whether discrete or continuous—are quantitatively analysed, offering insights into the dynamics at play within the system.

Likewise, based on the BN example generated for the CAT 775G, measurable variables can be quantified -originating from information theory and used in data science, such as mutual information, Shannon entropy, or Kullback-Leibler divergence- to determine the amount of information exchanged between the variables, their degree of certainty, and their predictive potential (see Table 15). Finally, once the model has been built and the relevance of the variables involved is established, different scenarios can be inferred, and the risk of an outlier event in equipment performance can be assessed.

Table 15. Example of relationship analysis for CAT 775G machine

Parent	Child	Kullback-Leibler divergence	Relative Weight	Contribution	Relative Mutual Information
fuelLevel	engineHours	0.7993	1.0000	15.94%	41.13%
engineHours	engineTotalFuelUsed	0.6387	0.7992	12.74%	50.34%
engineHours	speed	0.5769	0.7218	11.51%	30.52%
engineRpm	acceleratorPedalPosition	0.5411	0.6770	10.79%	34.27%
acceleratorPedalPosition	engineLoad	0.5028	0.6291	10.03%	34.26%
speed	engineRpm	0.4554	0.5697	9.08%	25.97%
engineHours	ambientTemp	0.3721	0.4655	7.42%	20.42%
engineHours	in_zone	0.3412	0.4269	6.80%	16.10%

⁴ The color of the nodes outlines a conceptual clustering (human-based).

engineRpm	VhStatus	0.3105	0.3884	6.19%	25.28%
engineHours	gpsQuality	0.2031	0.2541	4.05%	10.38%
fuelLevel	TotalHours	0.1963	0.2456	3.92%	10.07%
VhStatus	EngineOnOff	0.0460	0.0575	0.92%	22.82%
acceleratorPedalPosition	brakePosition	0.0308	0.0385	0.61%	3.43%

5.5.2.2 Impact on energy efficiency

The application of BNs in the DEQ development can be particularly useful in high-energy consumption scenarios, they help link operational factors to their effects on equipment, guiding the development of effective mitigation strategies. Their proven analytical capabilities are invaluable for detecting patterns and enhancing decision-making. It is expected that this translates into guidelines for a more efficient operation and an optimisation of fuel usage.

5.5.2.3 Other impacts

5.5.2.3.1 Productivity

Further analysis through machine learning techniques provides valuable insight for improving the efficiency and productivity of the operation.

5.5.2.3.2 Environment

Enhanced productivity and optimal fuel consumption translate directly into GHG emissions reduction.

5.5.2.3.3 Social acceptance

An operation that works towards the mitigation of its impacts, such as GHG emissions, can achieve an enhanced perception from communities and stakeholders in general, leading to greater social acceptance.

5.5.2.4 Limitations and future work

These models are being tested based on their precision, accuracy, and interpretability. Throughout this task, the explanatory power of all models for detecting, preventing, and characterising inefficient processes will be leveraged, utilising the well-established inferential and interpretive abilities of Bayesian algorithms.

MUL's efforts focus on unlocking the whole potential of the data generated by the different expert systems along the quarrying value chain in DEQ. The primary focus is on fuel consumption reduction supported by the mobile machinery data provided by Abaut and DH&P (see sections 5.2.2 and 5.2.3). However, further analysis during the development of the DEQ project can include expanding the scope of AI application to connect these variables with other unit processes, up and downstream the value chain.

5.6 Summary

The solutions developed within the DEQ project address each unit process of the quarrying value chain. The technologies described in this report are the ones that directly impact energy efficiency. However, more solutions are part of the DEQ developments, addressing other key matters such as safety and environmental aspects⁵.

A summary of the solutions described in this report is presented in Table 16. As illustrated throughout this section, these technologies have the potential to enhance energy efficiency both locally, i.e. at a specific unit process, and globally, i.e.

⁵ More information available on DEQ's website: <https://digiecoquarry.eu/>

overall operation optimisation. It is important to mention, however, that most of the expected energy reductions are still theoretical, based on laboratory tests and/or past experiences in similar applications. The actual improvements will be evaluated during the remaining phase of the project, and the results may vary between quarries, within DEQ and in future applications, depending on the specific circumstances of each operation.

Finally, many of these solutions can positively impact other aspects of quarrying activity, such as increased productivity, enhanced safety, reduced environmental impact, and improved social acceptance.

In the following section, an integral evaluation of the DEQ’s impact on energy efficiency is provided.

Table 16. Overview of DEQ solutions towards energy consumption reduction

Process in the value chain	Partner	System	Type	Scope of impact on energy efficiency	Potential consumption reduction		Other positive impacts			
					Fuel	Electricity	Productivity	Safety	Environment	Social acceptance
Drilling	Sandvik	XL-method	Drill rig	Local	16%	N/A	✓	✓	✓	✓
Blasting	MAXAM	X-Energy	Smart blasting	Local & downstream	5-10% (loading)	2-5% (crushing)	✓	✓	✓	✓
Pre-crushing	Metso	Lokotrack LT1213SE	Mobile crusher	Local	15%	N/A	✓	✓	✓	✓
Hauling	Abaut	Abaut	HW/SW for fleet monitoring	Local	5-10%	N/A	✓	✓	✓	✓
	DH&P	AutoPLAN	HW/SW for fleet monitoring	Local	TBD	N/A	✓	✓	✓	✓
Processing	Arco	Weighing systems	HW/SW for plant optimisation	Local	N/A	TBD	✓	✓	✓	
	Ma-estro	Ma-estro	HW/SW for plant optimisation	Local	N/A	10-15%	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Mintek	Digital Twin	Digital twin	Local	N/A	TBD	✓	✓	✓	
Cross-sectional analysis	UPM-M & MAXAM	Drill-to-mill	Data analysis	Overall	TBD	TBD	✓	✓	✓	
	MUL	ML-BN	Data analysis	Local	TBD	TBD	✓		✓	✓

6 DEQ's impact on energy efficiency

6.1 ICT energy consumption

Worldwide, the information and communication technology (ICT) sector has experienced significant growth over the past decades, and with it, its share of global energy consumption. While by 2012, ICT was estimated to represent approximately 3.9% of the electricity consumed globally (van Heddeghem et al. 2014), more recent estimations indicate a share closer to 8% of the total (Jha et al. 2023), and further growth is expected in the future.

To properly assess the benefits of the DEQ solutions pack regarding energy efficiency, it is necessary to also consider the energy consumed due to the digitalisation process that this project involves, i.e. electricity consumed by the networks and servers that allow the functioning of the smart tools and systems in DEQ.

6.1.1 Methodology

The approach to estimating the electricity usage attributable to DEQ consists of the following steps:

1. Quantify the data transfers between the technologies implemented on-site (see section 5), expert systems, IQS, Power BI dashboards⁶
2. Quantify the data storage requirements for the expert systems and the IQS
3. Quantify the electricity consumed by computing tasks performed by some of the DEQ expert systems in specialised additional PC units installed on-site or in the system's servers
4. Apply electricity intensity factors to estimate the energy consumption of such data transfers and data storage

Accordingly, the assumptions considered for the calculations are:

1. Hypothetical scenario in which all DEQ solutions are implemented in one given quarry
2. Calculations based on a one-year basis
3. Operational assumptions:
 - a. 10 hours-shifts
 - b. 240 operative days per year
 - c. 30 boreholes per blast
 - d. 52 blasts per year
 - e. 10 machines in mobile fleet
4. Electricity intensity factors (SG Andrae 2020; Aslan et al. 2018):

a. Data transmission (fixed access wired network):	0.070 kWh/GB
b. Data transmission (wireless access network):	0.180 kWh/GB
c. Data storage in data centres:	0.015 kWh/GB

6.1.2 Data transfer

The DEQ project combines a series of technologies deployed at the sites, software components of each technology and digital services offered by other partners (onwards, both referred to as expert systems), Power BI dashboards, and the IQS

⁶ Management tools included in the DEQ project have been implemented in Power BI to provide the quarry staff with relevant KPIs and valuable insight into the operations.

at the core of the data flow. A simplified data flow model⁷ is presented in Figure 33. In the diagram, the relevant data flows considered in this estimation are represented by the grey arrows.

Figure 33. Simplified DEQ data flow model

Figure 34 presents the annual data transfer related to the technologies on-site by unit process, according to what is described in section 5. The largest data transfer volume is represented by the loading and hauling processes, specifically by the monitoring systems implemented in the mobile machinery⁸. This is highly influenced by the functionalities that involve image capturing in these solutions.

Figure 34. Data transfer by process

Likewise, Figure 35 shows the yearly data flow of the different digital services implemented within DEQ. Since they do not directly impact energy efficiency, they have not been addressed in this report. However, their data transfer and data storage requirements must be considered in the ICT energy consumption estimation. From the figure, it is possible to observe that the data transfer is minor compared to the technologies on-site: maximums are about 70 times lower.

⁷ For more information on the IQS design, architecture, and other digital services, please refer to deliverables D4.2 and D4.6 available on DEQ’s website: <https://digiecoquarry.eu/deliverables/>.

⁸ Given that two different monitoring systems for mobile machinery have been developed within DEQ, only the maximum value has been considered for the data quantification in each case (conservative estimation).

Figure 35. Data transfer by digital solution and corresponding partner

6.1.3 Data storage

The expert systems of technologies on-site, as well as those of the digital services, require that certain data is periodically stored for their correct functioning. Figure 36 and Figure 37 present the annual data storage requirements for the technologies on-site and digital services, correspondingly. Similarly to the data flow, data storage requirements are by far larger on the productive technologies than the digital services, especially in the loading and hauling monitoring systems.

Figure 36. Data storage requirement by process

Figure 37. Data storage requirement by digital solution and corresponding partner

Likewise, the IQS and its sub-systems incorporate storage capacity that must be considered in this estimation. As it can be observed in Figure 38, the IQS includes significant capacity in order to support and integrate all the systems developed within the DEQ project.

Figure 38. Data storage capacity of IQS sub-systems developed by AKKODIS

Finally, Table 17 summarises the data transfer and storage by system and the corresponding shares in the total.

Table 17. Summary data transfer and data storage by system

System	Data transfer [GB/year]	Data storage [GB/year]	Share in total data transfer [%]	Share in total data storage [%]
Technologies on-site	299.04	179.71	98.24	56.13
Digital services	5.37	1.93	1.76	0.60
IQS	0.01	138.50	0.00	43.26
Total	304.42	320.13		

6.1.4 Computing tasks

Additionally to data transfer and storage, energy consumption due to computing tasks is also considered in the electricity usage attributable to the DEQ project. Four services involve relevant computing tasks:

- **ITK-Safety systems:** object detection system on-site includes a camera, a Jetson Orin board, and a mobile internet access point
- **Roctim-Plantsmith:** Roctim’s server⁹
 - Simulation computing: 80s (one time when the model is implemented in the simulator)
 - Computing time to fetch data from the IQS, calculate, and send to IQS: 10s (monthly)
- **Sigma-Quality & grain size:** dedicated PC installed in the quarry. Utilisation of 20%, full-time
- **Sigma-MetaQuarry:** deployed in Sigma’s Server. Utilization of 50%, computing time per query of 3s, 10 queries per day

The electricity consumed by these tasks is summarised in Table 18.

Table 18. Electricity consumed by computing tasks

Digital service	Computing times [h/year]	PC/server power [W]	Electricity consumption [kWh]
ITK-Safety systems	2,400	70	168
Roctim-Plantsmith	0.056	450	0.025
Sigma-Quality & grain size	1,752	500	876
Sigma-MetaQuarry	1	400	0.4

6.1.5 Electricity usage

As stated in section 6.1.1, the electricity consumption attributable to data transfer and storage is calculated by applying the corresponding factors. Table 19 summarises these results, together with the electricity consumed by computing tasks and the corresponding shares in the totals.

Table 19. ICT electricity consumption estimation by system and category

System	Data transfer [kWh]	Data storage [kWh]	Computing tasks [kWh]	Total [kWh]
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⁹ See Asbjörnsson et al. 2024 for more information on data integration between Plantsmith and the IQS for environmental impact monitoring.

Technologies on-site	26.55	3.16	-	29.71
Digital services	0.38	0.03	1,086.25	1,086.65
IQS	0.00	2.08	-	2.08
Total	26.93	5.27	1,086.25	1,118.44

Finally, it has been estimated that approximately 1,118 kWh per year of electricity consumption can be attributed to the digital components of DEQ solutions, i.e. data transfer, storage, and computing tasks. From these, computing tasks in digital services represent the largest share of the consumption, as can be observed in Figure 39.

Figure 39. ICT electricity consumption distribution by system and category

In the context of a quarrying operation, taking as reference the DEQ’s pilot sites, the ICT electricity consumption per processed tonne would be in the range of 0.0007-0.0024 kWh/t, significantly lower than the global specific consumption of these operations, which by 2023 was between 1.2 and 2.9 kWh/t.

As expected, the ICT electricity usage, though not completely negligible, is minor in the overall quarrying operation, equivalent to 0.06%-0.08% of the yearly total electricity consumption.

6.2 Integral evaluation

In section 5, the potential energy efficiency improvement that can be achieved by implementing each DEQ solution was described. The specific contributions are summarised in Table 16, section 5.6.

Based on these potential energy efficiency improvements, two enhanced scenarios are defined, expected and optimistic. Each scenario considers a percentage of energy consumption reduction, fuel and electricity, as presented in Table 20.

Table 20. Energy efficiency scenarios

Energy source	Current scenario	Expected scenario	Optimistic scenario	Reduction mechanisms
Fuel	0% variation	5% reduction	10% reduction	Improved blasting, mobile fleet monitoring and optimisation
Electricity	0% variation	5% reduction	15% reduction	Improved blasting, plant optimisation

6.2.1 Economic impact

From an economic perspective, the reduction in energy consumption translates into lower operational costs. Table 21 presents the relevance of such a reduction in the OPEX of the pilot sites in DEQ¹⁰.

Table 21. Average share of OPEX represented by the expected and optimistic energy consumption reductions

Energy source	OPEX reduction in the expected scenario	OPEX reduction in the optimistic scenario
Fuel	0.83%	2.48%
Electricity	0.96%	3.82%
Overall	1.78%	6.30%

To comprehensively assess the economic impact of DEQ solution, other elements need to be considered, e.g., increase in productivity, potential lower expenses on materials and consumables (such as explosives), and the CAPEX and OPEX difference between traditional technologies and the smart tools included in DEQ's systems. Though this is out of the scope of this report, the figures presented in Table 21 give a first estimation of the economic relevance of improving energy efficiency at a quarrying operation.

6.2.2 Environmental impact

Though other secondary positive impacts, e.g., reduced water consumption, can be expected, this assessment focuses on GHG emissions. To assess the impact of energy efficiency improvements due to the DEQ project, the yearly CO₂ emissions associated with energy consumption have been calculated for the current, expected, and optimistic scenarios.

A factor of 2.68 kg CO₂/L has been considered for fuel consumption (diesel). Regarding the CO₂ emissions due to electricity consumption, country-specific supplier mix factors based on AIB (2023) have been applied according to the pilot sites' locations. These range from 171 (Spain) to 364 (Portugal) g CO₂/kWh.

Figure 40 presents the average expected and optimistic CO₂ emissions reduction due to energy efficiency improvements¹¹. The calculations also consider the emissions associated with the energy consumption of the ICT systems in DEQ.

Figure 40. Potential impact on energy-related CO₂ emissions from the implementation of DEQ

¹⁰ Based on 2022 data for CEMEX, CIMPOR, and HOLCIM pilot sites.

¹¹ Based on 2022 data for CEMEX, CIMPOR, and HOLCIM pilot sites.

From these results, the main takeaways are:

- Approximately a 5% reduction in the CO₂ emissions associated with energy consumption can be expected from the implementation of DEQ solutions
- This reduction, in a quarry of the scale of the Valdilecha-CEMEX or Alenquer-CIMPOR, could mean approximately 100 to 120 fewer tonnes of CO₂ emissions per year
- Moreover, in an optimistic scenario, almost a 12% CO₂ energy-related emission reduction could be achieved, equivalent to an amount in the range of 220-260 fewer tonnes of CO₂ per year
- Overall, the emissions corresponding to the electricity consumption of DEQ's ICT tools are by far compensated by the potential reductions in fuel and electricity consumption

Finally, and as mentioned before, these results are based on theoretical potential energy consumption reductions. The actual improvements will be validated during the remaining phase of the DEQ project. Likewise, energy efficiency gains to be achieved in future applications of DEQ solutions may also vary depending on the specific circumstances of the operations, as has been explained throughout the report.

7 Conclusions

Energy efficiency is one of the main focuses of attention in the DEQ project, given its importance from both economic and environmental perspectives. The approach followed in this regard has covered from analysing the origin, i.e. energy generation and specifically the adoption of renewable energy technologies in the aggregate sector, to developing innovative technologies aimed at improving energy efficiency along the quarrying value chain.

The uptake of renewable energy sources by quarries is strongly dependent on local conditions. Individual approaches by companies may vary; however, a series of key factors have been identified. Based on these factors, a general guideline has been proposed to support the decision-making process of quarries evaluating embarking on a renewable energy project.

DEQ solutions show great potential to enhance energy efficiency in all aspects of the quarrying cycle (extraction, material handling, processing, and auxiliary technologies). Considering the expected improvements introduced by each tool, a quarry implementing DEQ technologies has the potential to achieve annual CO₂ energy-related emissions reductions in the range of 5% to 12%.

Finally, the energy consumption associated with the ICT component of the DEQ project has also been estimated. The results show that implementing these digital infrastructure and services pays off. They are effective tools for improving the operational performance and environmental impact monitoring of quarries while consuming a significantly minor amount of energy in comparison to the potential savings that can be achieved through them.

8 References

- Ackermann, Thomas (2012): Wind power in power systems. 2nd ed. Edited by Thomas Ackermann. Chichester, West Sussex: John Wiley & Sons.
- AIB (2023): European Residual Mixes: Results of the calculation of Residual Mixes for the calendar year 2022. Available online at <https://www.aib-net.org/facts/european-residual-mix/2022>, checked on 5/8/2024.
- Alova, Galina (2018): Integrating renewables in mining : review of business models and policy implications. Edited by OECD Publishing (No. 14).
- Antofagasta PLC (2020): Articles. Available online at <https://www.antofagasta.co.uk/media/articles/switching-to-renewable-energy/>, checked on 2/9/2024.
- Aprà, Fabio Maria; Smit, Sander; Sterling, Raymond; Loureiro, Tatiana (2021): Overview of the Enablers and Barriers for a Wider Deployment of CSP Tower Technology in Europe. In *Clean Technol.* 3 (2), pp. 377–394. DOI: 10.3390/cleantechnol3020021.
- Aramendia, Emmanuel; Brockway, Paul E.; Taylor, Peter G.; Norman, Jonathan (2023): Global energy consumption of the mineral mining industry: Exploring the historical perspective and future pathways to 2060. In *Global Environmental Change* 83, p. 102745. DOI: 10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2023.102745.
- ARENA (2017): Time to ditch the generator? The town where renewables took over. In *Australian Renewable Energy Agency (ARENA)*, 2017. Available online at <https://arena.gov.au/blog/coober-pedy-solar-farm/>, checked on 4/5/2024.
- Asbjörnsson, Gauti; Sköld, Adam; Zougari, Sadeq; Yar, Ann-Gaelle; Kamel, Nemer; Turlur-Chabanon, Sophie et al. (2024): Development of production and environmental platforms for the European aggregates and minerals industries. In *Minerals Engineering* 206, p. 108519.
- Ashat, Ali; Pratama, Heru Berian; Itoi, Ryuichi (2019): Comparison of resource assessment methods with numerical reservoir model between heat stored and experimental design: case study Ciwidey-Patuha geothermal field. In *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.* 254 (1), p. 12011. DOI: 10.1088/1755-1315/254/1/012011.
- Aslan, Joshua; Mayers, Kieren; Koomey, Jonathan G.; France, Chris (2018): Electricity intensity of internet data transmission: Untangling the estimates. In *Journal of industrial ecology* 22 (4), pp. 785–798.
- Awuah-Offei, Kwame (2016): Energy efficiency in mining: a review with emphasis on the role of operators in loading and hauling operations. In *Journal of Cleaner Production* 117, pp. 89–97.
- Bakhtavar, E.; Aghayarloo, R.; Yousefi, S.; Hewage, K.; Sadiq, R. (2019): Renewable energy based mine reclamation strategy: A hybrid fuzzy-based network analysis. In *Journal of Cleaner Production* 230, pp. 253–263. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.05.073.
- Banerjee, Sudeshna Ghosh; Romo, Zayra; McMahon, Gary; Toledano, Perrine; Pérez Arroyo, Inés (2015): The Power of the Mine : A Transformative Opportunity for Sub-Saharan Africa. Directions in Development. Edited by Energy and Mining. Washington. Available online at <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/entities/publication/bac8f472-f904-58cf-af04-2850cabb4578>, checked on 3/4/2024.
- Bene, Csinszka (2023): Solving the energy storage problem for a clean energy system. In *SDG Action*, 2023. Available online at <https://sdg-action.org/solving-the-energy-storage-problem-for-a-clean-energy-system/>, checked on 4/17/2024.
- Ceran, B.; Szczerbowski, R. (2019): Energy cost analysis by hybrid power generation system. In *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.* 214, p. 12001. DOI: 10.1088/1755-1315/214/1/012001.
- Cetinay, Hale; Kuipers, Fernando A.; Guven, A. Nezh (2017): Optimal siting and sizing of wind farms. In *Renewable Energy* 101, pp. 51–58. DOI: 10.1016/j.renene.2016.08.008.

Chan, Daniel; Mo, John (2017): Life Cycle Reliability and Maintenance Analyses of Wind Turbines. In *Energy Procedia* 110, pp. 328–333. DOI: 10.1016/j.egypro.2017.03.148.

Choi, Yosoon; Song, Jinyoung (2017): Review of photovoltaic and wind power systems utilized in the mining industry. In *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 75, pp. 1386–1391. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2016.11.127.

Clothworthy, A. W.; Ussher, G. N. H.; Lawless, J. V.; Randle, J. B. (2006): Geothermal resources. Securing our energy future : Geothermal Resources Council 2006 Annual Meeting, September 10-13, 2006, Town and Country Resort & Convention Center, San Diego, California, USA. Geothermal Resources Council. Davis, Calif (GRC transactions).

Copper Alliance (2022): Antofagasta's Copper Production Powered by 100 Percent Renewable Energy - Copper Alliance. Available online at <https://copperalliance.org/resource/antofagastas-copper-production-powered-by-100-percent-renewable-energy/>, checked on 2/9/2024.

Cristian Paul Chioncel; Chioncel Petru; Nicoleta Gillich (2011): Overview of Classic and Modern Wind Measurement Techniques, Basis of Wind Project Development. In *1453-7397 XVIII* (3), pp. 73–80. Available online at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259952626_Overview_of_Classic_and_Modern_Wind_Measurement_Techniques_Basis_of_Wind_Project_Development.

Eleni Patsa; Dirk Van Zyl; Sadiq J Zarrouk; Nastaran Arianpoo (2015): Geothermal Energy in Mining Developments: Synergies and Opportunities Throughout a Mine's Operational Life Cycle. In. *Proceedings World Geothermal Congress 2015*; Melbourne, Australia. Available online at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/269395965_Geothermal_Energy_in_Mining_Developments_Synergies_and_Opportunities_Throughout_a_Mine%27s_Operational_Life_Cycle.

Energy and mines (2014): Raglan Mine: Canada's First Industrial-Scale Wind and Energy Storage Facility. Available online at <https://energyandmines.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/08/Raglan.pdf>, checked on 5/23/2024.

European Aggregates Association (2021): Annual Review: 2020–2021 (European Aggregates Association: Brussels, Belgium).

European Commission (2024): The European Green Deal. Available online at https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en, checked on 4/19/2024.

Gacitúa, Jorge A.; Palma-Behnke, Rodrigo; Cardemil, José M.; Cerda, María Teresa; Godoy, Felipe; Dinter, Frank (2022): Assessing the synergy between a seawater pumping system for mining facilities and the cooling system of a CSP plant in Northern Chile. In *Journal of Cleaner Production* 346, p. 131052.

Glencore Canada (2023): Green and clean energy. Available online at <https://www.glencore.ca/en/raglan/sustainability/environment/Environment---Green-and-clean-energy>, checked on 2/14/2024.

Guo, Lidan; Zhou, Haiwei; Xia, Ziqiang; Huang, Feng (2016): Evolution, opportunity and challenges of transboundary water and energy problems in Central Asia. In *SpringerPlus* 5 (1), p. 1918. DOI: 10.1186/s40064-016-3616-0.

Holmberg, Kenneth; Kivikytö-Reponen, Päivi; Härkisaari, Pirita; Valtonen, Kati; Erdemir, Ali (2017): Global energy consumption due to friction and wear in the mining industry. In *Tribology International* 115, pp. 116–139. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2017.05.010.

Holmberg, Roger; Persson, Per-Anders (1978): The Swedish approach to contour blasting: SveDeFo.

Hussain, Athar; Batra, Ankit; Pachauri, Rupendra (2017): An experimental study on effect of dust on power loss in solar photovoltaic module. In *Renewables* 4 (1), pp. 1–13. DOI: 10.1186/s40807-017-0043-y.

IEA (2015): Projected Costs of Generating Electricity 2015. Paris. Available online at <https://www.iea.org/reports/projected-costs-of-generating-electricity-2015>, checked on 5/23/2024.

illuminem (2023): Harnessing the earth's energy: Pros and cons of geothermal power plants | illuminem. Available online at <https://illuminem.com/illuminemvoices/harnessing-the-earths-energy-pros-and-cons-of-geothermal-power-plants>, checked on 4/23/2024.

IRENA (2023a): Renewable power generation costs in 2022. Edited by International Renewable Energy Agency. Abu Dhabi.

IRENA (2023b): World Energy Transitions Outlook 2023: 1.5°C Pathway. Volume 1. Edited by IRENA. IRENA. Abu Dhabi. Available online at https://mc-cd8320d4-36a1-40ac-83cc-3389-cdn-endpoint.azureedge.net/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2023/Jun/IRENA_World_energy_transitions_outlook_v1_2023.pdf?rev=cc4522ff897a4e26a47906447c74bca6, checked on 12/31/2023.

Issi, Fatih; Kaplan, Orhan (2018): The Determination of Load Profiles and Power Consumptions of Home Appliances. In *Energies* 11 (3), p. 607. DOI: 10.3390/en11030607.

Jha, Abhishek Kumar Rajesh; Andrae, Anders S. G.; Mainali, Brijesh (2023): Comparison of Methods for Calculating Indirect Upstream Carbon Emissions from Information and Communication Technology Manufacturing. In *WSEAS TRANSACTIONS ON ENVIRONMENT AND DEVELOPMENT* 19, pp. 1045–1057.

Laing O'Rourke (2018): SunSHIFT to develop Australia's second largest solar hybrid system. Available online at <https://www.laingorourke.com/company/news/2018/sunshift-to-develop-australias-second-largest-solar-hybrid-system/>, checked on 2/13/2024.

Maennling, Nicolas; Toledano, Perrine (2018): The Renewable Power of the Mine. In *SSRN Journal*. DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.3661616.

Mining weekly (2018): Abandoned mines punted as potential pumped-storage scheme sites. Available online at <https://www.miningweekly.com/print-version/cumbersome-old-mines-potential-sites-for-pumped-hydro-energy-storage-genex-power-2018-02-09>, checked on 4/8/2024.

New European Wind Atlas (2022): Welcome to the New European Wind Atlas. Available online at <https://map.neweuropeanwindatlas.eu/>, checked on 4/22/2024.

Newcrest (2023): 2023 Sustainability report. Available online at https://www.newcrest.com/investor-centre/results-reports?report_type=8, checked on 2/12/2024.

Nodoph, Laura (2023): Guideline: The European Green Deal and Sustainability Regulation emerging from it. In *Makersite GmbH*, 2023. Available online at <https://makersite.io/insights/guideline-european-sustainability-regulation/>, checked on 4/19/2024.

OECD (2019): Global Material Resources Outlook to 2060 Economic Drivers and Environmental Consequences.

Paredes Sánchez, José Pablo (2018): Solar energy applications in mining: a case study. In *Energy Efficiency in the Minerals Industry: Best Practices and Research Directions*, pp. 273–285.

Pascual, Sara; Lisbona, Pilar; Romeo, Luis M. (2022): Thermal Energy Storage in Concentrating Solar Power Plants: A Review of European and North American R&D Projects. In *Energies* 15 (22), p. 8570. DOI: 10.3390/en15228570.

Pertamina (2020): Success Of Emission Reduction Program Through Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) In PT Pertamina Geothermal Energy - Pertamina Geothermal Energy Tbk. Available online at <https://www.pge.pertamina.com/en/press-release/success-of-emission-reduction-program-through-clean-development-mechanism-cdm-in-pt-pertamina-geothermal-energy>, checked on 2/12/2024.

Renewables First (2024): How long do hydropower systems last ? - Renewables First. Available online at <https://renewablesfirst.co.uk/renewable-energy-technologies/hydropower/hydropower-learning-centreold/how-long-will-hydropower-systems-last/>, updated on 3/24/2016, checked on 4/23/2024.

- Reuters (2016): Chilean Copper Firms Look at Reworking Contracts to Tap Renewable Energy. In *Voice of America (VOA News)*, 2016. Available online at <https://www.voanews.com/a/chilean-copper-firms-look-reworking-contracts-renewable-energy/3627847.html>, checked on 4/5/2024.
- Sanchez, Felipe; Hartlieb, Philipp (2022): Addressing Energy Efficiency in Quarries—First Stage in the Development of a Holistic Approach. In : Proceedings SDIMI 10th International Conference 2022. SDIMI 2022: Sustainable Development in the Minerals Industry 10th International Conference.
- SG Andrae, Anders (2020): New perspectives on internet electricity use in 2030. In *Engineering and Applied Science Letter* 3 (2), pp. 19–31.
- Sodhi, Manbir; Banaszek, Lennart; Magee, Chris; Rivero-Hudec, Mercedes (2022): Economic Lifetimes of Solar Panels. In *Procedia CIRP* 105, pp. 782–787. DOI: 10.1016/j.procir.2022.02.130.
- Solargis (2024): Solar resource maps and GIS data for 200+ countries | Solargis. Available online at <https://solargis.com/maps-and-gis-data/download/portugal>, checked on 3/14/2024.
- Soni, Divyansh; Kundu, Amit Kumar; Gautam, Neeraj; Songade, Chetan; Patel, Vikrant Singh; Patil, Veerandra; Gupta, Rajeev (2022): Hydropower an Efficient Renewable Source of Energy: An Analysis.
- Stoll, Brady; Andrade, Juan; Cohen, Stuart; Brinkman Greg; Martinez-Anido, Carlo Brancucci (2017): Hydropower Modeling Challenges. Technical Report. Edited by National Renewable Energy Laboratory. National Renewable Energy Laboratory.
- Strazzabosco, A.; Gruenhagen, J. H.; Cox, S. (2022): A review of renewable energy practices in the Australian mining industry. In *Renewable Energy* 187, pp. 135–143. DOI: 10.1016/j.renene.2022.01.021.
- Tyagi, V. V.; Rahim, Nurul A.A.; Rahim, N. A.; Selvaraj, Jeyraj A./L. (2013): Progress in solar PV technology: Research and achievement. In *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 20, pp. 443–461. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2012.09.028.
- U.S. Department of Energy (2023): Land-Based Wind Market Report: 2023 Edition. Available online at <https://www.energy.gov/eere/wind/articles/land-based-wind-market-report-2023-edition>, checked on 2/16/2024.
- van Heddeghem, Ward; Lambert, Sofie; Lannoo, Bart; Colle, Didier; Pickavet, Mario; Demeester, Piet (2014): Trends in worldwide ICT electricity consumption from 2007 to 2012. In *Computer communications* 50, pp. 64–76.
- Vodapally, Sai Nikhil; Ali, Mohd Hasan (2023): A Comprehensive Review of Solar Photovoltaic (PV) Technologies, Architecture, and Its Applications to Improved Efficiency. In *Energies* 16 (1), p. 319. DOI: 10.3390/en16010319.
- World Bank (2021): Concentrating Solar Power: Clean Power on Demand 24/7. Washington, DC. Available online at [https://pubdocs.worldbank.org/en/849341611761898393/WorldBank-CSP-Report-Concentrating-Solar-Power-Clean-Power-on-Demand-24-7-FINAL.pdf#:~:text=URL%3A%20https%3A%2F%2Fpubdocs.worldbank.org%2Fen%2F849341611761898393%2FWorldBank,checked on 4/15/2024.](https://pubdocs.worldbank.org/en/849341611761898393/WorldBank-CSP-Report-Concentrating-Solar-Power-Clean-Power-on-Demand-24-7-FINAL.pdf#:~:text=URL%3A%20https%3A%2F%2Fpubdocs.worldbank.org%2Fen%2F849341611761898393%2FWorldBank,checked%20on%204%2F15%2F2024)
- Zharan, Kateryna; Bongaerts, Jan C. (2017): Decision-making on the integration of renewable energy in the mining industry: A case studies analysis, a cost analysis and a SWOT analysis. In *Journal of Sustainable Mining* 16 (4), pp. 162–170. DOI: 10.1016/j.jsm.2017.11.004.

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